

MASTER'S THESIS

Influence of the National Gross Diesel Price Index on
Agricultural and Food Price
Indices along the Value Chain in Austria

A Time-Series Analysis using a VAR-Model

submitted by

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Abstract

The following elaboration is concerned with an empirical study that is based on a project of the Austrian Institute of Economic Research (WIFO) that tries to identify a possible causal linkage between energy prices in the form of a self-created Gross Diesel Price Index on Food Price Indices of certain Food Product-Groups along the Value Chain for Austria. The steps along the value chain include the Agricultural Price Index (ACP), Import Price Index (IPI) and the Harmonized Index of Consumer Prices (HICP), and for all food products combined the Producer Price Index (PPI_d or PPI) as well. The Food Product Groups chosen were – Bread & Cereal, Oils & Fats, Meat Products and an Index of all Food Products combined of the EU's Food Price Monitoring tool as these represent a diverse mix of important Food Products for Austria.

A VAR-Model including Granger Causality Wald-tests was used as the time-series method with data ranging from January 2005 until March 2024.

The results show that the crude-oil based Gross Diesel Price Index has a significant influence, and granger causes most of the respective Food Price Indices along the value chain, except for Bread & Cereal ACP, Oils & Fats ACP and Food products PPI. However, the results reveal a bidirectional causality for Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereal products that can be traced back to biodiesel-production in Austria. It turns out that biodiesel is both mixed into the standard retail diesel and sold as pure biodiesel product as well and is produced largely by products, especially seeds from the Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereal product groups. Furthermore, when the sole influences of the product groups along the value chain are considered, the ACP index shows significant influence on the HICP with positive coefficient for all product groups but Oils & Fats. At last, policy advice on supporting Austrian farmers further is given with past price rises of diesel in mind.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AMA	Agrarmarkt Austria
BAB	Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen
BWB	Bundeswettbewerbsbehörde (Austria)
HICP	Harmonized Index of Consumer Prices
PPI	Producer Price Index
ACP	Price Index of Agricultural Products
IPI	International trade in Price Index or Import Price Index
ADF	Augmented Dickey Fuller test
GC	Granger Causality
LM-test	Lagrange-Multiplier test

1 INTRODUCTION

Food prices and energy prices are both important for economic and societal well-being of a nation. Lots of different literature already exists on the relationship between these two central commodities and their respective prices for several different nations – see also the Theoretical Background Part of this elaboration. The Austrian Institute of Economic Research (WIFO) published a report in April of 2024 in which the author of this Thesis was personally a part of as a Scientific Assistant (Renhart *et al.*, 2024). A key target of the report was concerned with finding best-practice examples of European countries that have high food price reporting standards. Since in Austria price reporting along the agricultural value chain is not as extensively done as for instance in France (Renhart *et al.*, 2024) where almost all agricultural prices along the value chain and per product group including by-products arising during the production process must be reported, there exists room for more transparent price reporting in the agricultural sector in Austria. Nevertheless, the report is, as is suggested in the word report instead of scientific paper, limited to reporting a collection of data sources from Austria and important agricultural countries of the EU and making policy suggestion but no empirical study has been conducted. Additionally, a sample case or theoretical best-practice case for Austria has been introduced, which could improve data availability for all parties that are relying on such data (Renhart *et al.*, 2024) for fairness purposes. This could be for instance Research Institutions, but more importantly also participants along the value chain as for instance farmers, wholesale market sellers and buyers, producers and other participants of the value chain (BWB/BU Lebensmittel. Wien, 2022) that depend on price or cost reporting in the agricultural sector. Moreover, this elaboration tries to widen research on the topic of food or agricultural prices in Austria and focuses on one specific factor which could potentially have a causal impact on these prices: energy prices.

The motivation to focus on possible influences of energy prices on food prices is partly based on the Ukraine-Russia war, that possibly have influenced prices of crude oil-based products or e.g. wheat, and grain prices, also in Austria, and thus causal effects could have happened since the beginning of the war in February of 2022. Ukraine is one of the most important suppliers and thus fifth largest exporter of wheat worldwide (Devadoss and Ridley, 2024). Likewise, the energy market – oil prices specifically – have been affected hugely by the invasion of Russia into Ukraine in February 2022 (*ibid.*).

Furthermore, to clarify the research projects target, there is one general research question to be answered:

Does the Austrian Gross Diesel Price Index granger cause food and agricultural price indices along the value chain from January 2005 until March 2024?¹

Note here that in the third section of this Thesis the research question(s) will be specified in more detail. To visually better understand the concept of prices along the value chain, Figure 1 shall clarify this concept:

Figure 1: Agricultural and food value chain

Source: Created by Author, scheme inspired by (BWB/BU Lebensmittel. Wien, 2022; BAB, 2024; Eurostat, 2025).

Figure 1 shows a strongly abbreviated version of the general scheme of the whole value chain of food products and their respective prices – at least in Austria. Additionally, to the Food Price Indices used in this elaboration there exists a wholesale market for different product-groups marked on the lower right-hand corner in green in Figure 1.

¹ Note that granger causes refers to granger causality, which will be explained in more detail in the Methods section. For now, it is sufficient to compare the term with having a causal influence.

However, the Price Indices marked in red are used for the empirical study and they follow the trajectory indicated in Figure 1 from left to right. In addition, imported food products could have an influence along the National value chain as well, which is illustrated with the yellow box on the top right-hand corner in Figure 1.

The general intention of the empirical study conducted in this elaboration is that between all manufacturing steps and steps along the value chain for executing different tasks energy is needed, e.g. transportation, assembling or during production of the final retail products that consumers buy in the supermarkets, as well as for harvesting crops or simply maintenance of animal barns and so on. Besides, in this study only agricultural prices, consumer end prices and price indices of similar products that were imported were taken as variables for the quantitative empirical study. That is because, wholesale price indices were not published at the EU website where prices have been collected for the study. This marks a gap in the transparency of whole value chain, as will be discussed later on in the Thesis.

The most relevant institution to publish and register agricultural prices along the value chain in Austria, the AMA, which stands for Agrarmarkt Austria, generally differentiates between five different product groups for agricultural products, that are fruit & vegetables, Cereals & oilseeds, eggs & poultry, milk & milk-products and livestock & meat. Unfortunately, the WIFO report mentioned earlier (Renhart *et al.*, 2024) made clear that prices along the value have not been published consistently in Austria. Because of that price indices of the ACP, HICP, IPI – plus PPI for food products (see abbreviation section for meaning) – have been chosen for four different food product groups. Since Price Indices are able to represent a large number of products within one index, they were regarded as the best way to cover overall food products for Austria. The products groups chosen were: A combined-food-products index, Meat Products, Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereals.

In order to answer the research questions appropriately, a time-series model, namely a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model has been used for the empirical study. The timeframe covered ranges from January 2005 until March 2024 with 220 observations in total.

The following text is structured as follows: Section 2 consists of a Literature Review of the Theoretical Background which is relevant to explain economic theories and shed light on the importance of similar studies for the empirical study. Section 3 is concerned with

describing Data Sources and Methodology used in the study. Section 4 presents all relevant results. In Section 5 results are discussed and put into perspective and limitations are debated. Section 6 concludes and stresses once again the importance of supporting systems for local farmers in Austria concerning diesel or crude-oil based products inflation using policy tools.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

At first, general economic theory on the effect that energy prices can have on food prices in general in Economics is given. Secondly, the socioeconomic dimension of energy prices and food prices in the framework of societies is given to illustrate the social importance of the overall topic. Thirdly, Theoretical Background on the topic of energy prices and food prices is given in form of a Literature Review of similar research projects, that check for a possible causal linkage between energy prices and food prices for different regions and use various statistical methods to answer their specific research questions. Finally, an overview of these papers is given in Table 1.

2.1 General economic theory on food prices and energy prices

An important insight for energy price data in empirical studies is made by (Kirikkaleli and Darbaz, 2021): Usually similar scientific empirical studies that analyze the relationship between energy and food prices use crude oil or bioenergy-source as the energy price variable (ibid.) However, the authors use lots of different variables from the World Bank's Commodity Price Data in form of an energy index. In this index not only crude oil but also coal and natural gas prices are included.

In addition, to describe the economic effects that energy prices can have on food prices, this paper is useful. This is because several ways how energy prices can influence food prices are presented by the authors: Firstly, the supply side can be affected, for instance by production costs increasing. This means that the supply curve in the economic equilibrium case, where supply and demand curves cross each other at the equilibrium price and amount, [...] "shifts to the left, which means higher food prices." (Kirikkaleli and Darbaz, 2021, p.2). The economic representation of this cost rising case on the supply side can be observed in Figure 2. The economic intuition is the following: The higher energy prices increase energy costs and this ultimately leads to less products being sold due to lower production of food products with demand staying on an equal level as before and therefore prices of food are increasing. This is of course only the case if energy costs have a significant impact on the supply curve of the particular company or country.

Secondly, the demand side can also be influenced by energy prices and therefore costs increasing. For instance, increasing crude oil prices in combination with environmental concern have in the past been able to "encourage governments to support the energy crop production of farmers" (Kirikkaleli and Darbaz, 2021, p. 2). This results according to the

theory ultimately in high crude oil prices increasing the demand for biofuels, since the latter are supported by the government through subsidies. Consequently, the reason for oil prices increasing originates from the demand of crude oil being high. This in turn increases the prices of corn and soybeans and other crops. This is due to the fact that biofuels are for instance generated by corn and soybeans (Mahapatra *et al.*, 2021). In fact, biofuels “are referred to any fuel derived and produced from organic material such as plants and their residues, agricultural crops, by-products that can be an adequate substitute for petroleum-derived fuel.” (Mahapatra *et al.*, 2021, p.2) More on the use of biofuels is elaborated in the next section and the discussion section. This whole process results in the demand curve shifting to the right since demand for food – in this case for corn and soybeans – is increasing and therefore prices are rising. This relationship is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Supply and demand in cost rising case, with shifting supply-curve to the left

Source: created by author

These economic insights prove how interconnected the agricultural sector and thus the food sector is, which encourages the research hypothesis that energy prices have an impact on food prices along the value chain.

Nonetheless, this only shows the theoretical economical intuition behind the association of energy prices – in this case crude oil prices and biofuels – on agricultural products and food products. As shall be seen beginning in 2.3, this association has been analyzed empirically for various countries using various data sources and methods. The mentioning of biofuels used in agricultural production as an energy source however, introduced another important aspect of energy and food prices, that is the environmental as well as social impact of these prices. In the following section, this part shall be elaborated on.

Figure 3: Supply and demand with demand curve shifting due to increased demand

Source: created by author

2.2. Influence of energy or food prices on socioeconomic health of societies

Unexpectedly, the BWB (BWB/BU Lebensmittel. Wien, 2022) found out that already at the beginning of the war between Ukraine and Russia, starting on 24th of February 2022, worldwide inflation rates were rising, driven by rising energy prices. Likewise, these rising energy prices had effects on downstream markets such as markets for unprocessed and processed agricultural products. Hence, prices were also rising in these markets (ibid.). Since the general global inflation was already relatively high before the war, the reasons for high price rises cannot be alone explained by the war in Eastern Europe. Nevertheless, the war has accelerated inflation in sectors such as energy, agriculture and food markets where price changes have high impacts on the health or well-being of the respective societies as a whole. Concerning Austria, the monthly Consumer Price Index (CPI), which is collected by Statistik Austria (Statistik Austria, 2024), is divided into different subcategories. One of these subcategories is called "Nahrungsmittel und alkoholfreie Getränke (NAFG)" (BWB/BU Lebensmittel. Wien, 2022, p. 8) which accounts for around eleven percent of the whole CPI. This category has been rising more than the other categories of the CPI by 6.7 percent from January 2022 to December 2022. Moreover, the BWB analyzed the situation of 2022 for agricultural products along the value chain further and checked where exactly price increases were coming from along the value chain – including the producing sector and retail sector. (BWB/BU Lebensmittel. Wien, 2022). Furthermore, the European Commission conducted a research paper, analyzing the influence of energy price increases on households between the period of August 2021 and January 2023, focusing also on food price increases in the context of rising energy prices. (European Commission, 2023) The general results show that without “behavioral responses and direct income support for households – expenditure-based – energy [...] levels would have substantially increased across the EU because of energy price changes between August 2021 and January 2023, compared to the previous 18 months” (ibid. p. 3). Thus, energy price and food price increases, have had a significant impact on the lives of people living in EU countries. Only through governmental actions and behavioral changes in people’s lives has this impact been able to mitigate.

Another important factor when considering the influence of energy prices on the well-being of societies are crude oil prices. According to (Roman, Górecka and Domagała, 2020) crude oil prices have a “broad scope of applications” since they are important for “various sectors of economies including agriculture, transportation, and industry, as well

as households”. (Roman, Górecka and Domagała, 2020, p. 1) They influence fuel prices and therefore are potentially influencing other sectors as well. “Therefore, people’s quality of life shifts up and down when the price of crude oil is unbalanced and irrational.” (ibid., p. 1)

Moreover, following (Mahapatra *et al.*, 2021) biofuels are more and more needed and demanded since greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions have been rising in recent times and there has been an increasing search for substitutional products for common GHG-intensive fossil fuels based on crude oil products, such as diesel and petrol. Nonetheless, biofuels use a considerable amount of space to grow and therefore come with disadvantages of deforestation and inland usage (ibid.).

Further, following (Janda and Křišťoufek, 2019) significant biofuels were introduced in 2005 in several countries around the world. Thus, the price transmission between food prices and fossil fuels increased afterwards. This strengthens the intuitively already expected linkage between fuel prices over food prices for the case of biofuels. The results of the study by (Janda and Křišťoufek, 2019) show that biofuel pathways follow separate pathways in a sense that they are guided by domestic policies, as is the case for Austria as well (FCIO - Fachverband der Chemischen Industrie Österreichs, 2025). As the EIA pointed out in 2019, biofuels accounted for 5% of the US transportation sectors energy consumption in 2018 in the US, with ethanol’s share of about 4 % and biodiesel share of about 1%. Moreover, “the EU is still the main producer of biodiesel with expected production of about 13 billion L in 2027.” ((Janda and Křišťoufek, 2019, p. 199). Following the EU, the US has the second place and Brazil is the third worldwide (ibid.).

Besides, according to (Anuradha Mittal, 2009) there has been a food price crisis taking place in 2008, which had different initiators. – One of them was extensively discussed in the literature: That is the influence of energy prices rising and therefore costs increasing for certain food products. (ibid.) This is an example of the beforementioned case where the supply side is changing due to increasing costs of production in the value chain. (see 2.1). For instance, corn, soybeans and wheat prices in the United States have been affected with an increase in production costs by around 21.7 percent by prices doubling of energy intensive components within the value chain like fuels and fertilizer between 2002 and 2007 (Mitchell, D., 2008).

Moreover, governmental support for biofuels from the EU and the US in the 2000s and increasing demand for grains due to biofuels production in the EU and US both show an

example for demand side price shocks of energy prices on food prices. “70-75 percent increase in food commodities prices was due to biofuels and the related consequences” (Mitchell, D., 2008, p.17) from January 2002 – June 2008. This shows the consequences that the demand side, in this case in the form of an energy price of biofuels, can have for price equilibria of food prices.

Although these insights are helpful in terms of economic intuition and potential bio-fuel substitutes already had an impact in the past on energy and food prices (Mitchell, D., 2008; Anuradha Mittal, 2009; Mahapatra *et al.*, 2021), the following section provides a crucial part for the empirical study performed in this Thesis with different papers presented, that conducted similar studies on the influence of energy prices on food prices.

2.3 Crucial studies on the linkage between energy prices and food prices

In general, the studies described in this section are all using a time-series methods in their empirical study. The reason for this is that for this elaboration also a time-series method has been chosen, in the form of a VAR model. It is therefore helpful, to present these similar papers with partly different results and methods to the empirical study conducted in this Thesis.

Also, the following papers are ranging between different timespans and locations. The latter span from the US, over India to Brazil, China and so forth. The results indicate that an influence of energy prices on food prices depends on the time frame observed, the location where the empirical study has been conducted and the statistical method used. This is because the results range from energy prices having no influence, as for instance (Hussain, N. E., Shaari, M. S., & Abdullah, D. N. C., 2018) showed, to having a significant causal influence in the long-term or in the short-term for several different food categories.

Further evidence on study results depending on data, location and method used is provided by (Alom, F., Ward, B.D., & Hu, B., 2011). This paper focuses on spillover effects from mean and volatility of world oil prices on food prices of Asian and Pacific countries such as: Australia, New Zealand, South Korea, Singapore, Hong Kong, Taiwan, India and Thailand (*ibid.*). The models used range from VAR models and GARCH models, that is Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity models. The expected effects were found in the short run for all countries but with different magnitudes. In addition, stronger mean and volatility effects for the period from 2002 and 2010 compared to the

previous period observed ranging from 1995 – 2001 suggest growing interdependence for world oil and the respective countries over time.

Interestingly, (Hussain, N. E., Shaari, M. S., & Abdullah, D. N. C., 2018) use a timeframe that ranges for only 6 years on a monthly scale which results in only 72 observations used and might mitigate the informative long-term value of the study. On the other hand, similar studies used data over more than 30 years: (Obadi, S., Korcek, M., 2014) used monthly data for commodity prices from the World Bank from January 1975 until September 2013, resulting in 465 observations. As for the timespan of other papers: (Gilbert, 2010) is focusing especially on the large commodity price increases of the period between 2005-2008. Nevertheless, most papers that had similar research questions, had a similar time-range as the empirical study presented in this elaboration, that consists of about 19 years in monthly format, resulting in 230 observations in total per variable. Besides, it is noticeable that for most of the papers only around six variables overall were included in the respective studies, with crude oil prices being the most common energy variable.

(Ma, Xu and Dong, 2015) also used the Granger Causality Wald test approach to test the long-run causal relationship between world crude oil prices combined with the RMB-dollar exchange rate for five different agricultural commodity prices from China. The results of (Ma, Xu and Dong, 2015) show that the oil price changes in the long run show no sign of significantly influencing agricultural prices in China. Furthermore, the exchange rate of RMB-dollar only causally influences the soybean price, while maize, wheat, colza oil and japonica rice show no significant linkage with crude oil prices. Since the data was gathered weekly from June 2002 to August 2013, this provides a relatively large number of total observations with over 550 observations over a time of eleven years. (Derindag *et al.*, 2023) use global and national factors of India to check for possible associative relationships of these factors on food prices in India. The aim of the authors has been to conduct a research study, that examines influences of local and global factors on food prices in India using the Wavelet Coherence (WC), Granger Causality in Quantiles (GCQ) and at last the Quantile Regression (QR) “to determine how reliable the findings are”, (Derindag *et al.*, 2023, p. 1). This means that not only energy prices were taken as independent factors but rather also different potentially influencing variables. Especially India, according to the authors an underdeveloped country, is a place where food prices play a very important role for the whole consumer basket that is used to measure consumer prices (*ibid.*). For instance, approximately 25.94% of all consumer prices were

comprised of food prices, compared to Austria's eleven percent (Statistik Austria, 2024). The authors used three local and six global variables as independent variables for the models resulting in 9 independent variables as a whole. The WC results show that there is "a substantial association between local prices of food and independent factors across various frequencies and times." (Derindag *et al.*, 2023, p.1) As for the conceptual idea of looking at potentially independent factors and how they can influence food prices, several examples are being named, such as interest rates that potentially influence food prices by companies taking out less loans and therefore producing less because of having to pay back more interest rates. Hence, the supply of food is decreasing, and prices are rising (ibid.) The same concept can be found for oil prices as an example of energy prices, because they can drive up costs of companies that produce food, as was seen in the 2.1. Interestingly, (Derindag *et al.*, 2023, p. 4) write in their literature review that "researchers discovered that energy prices had a significant impact on food prices." (Derindag *et al.*, 2023, p. 4) Furthermore, three research hypothesis are being set up and the literatures distinctive contribution is the illumination of "[...] the connection between independent factors and prices of foods across various frequencies, quantiles, and timeframes." (Derindag *et al.*, 2023, p. 8)). The results show that almost all independent factors such as oil price, temperature, interest rate, raw material prices do not conform with linearity according to the BDS-test. Nevertheless, the WC-approach in the end, showed a crucial connection between regional Indian food prices and the independent explanatory factors (ibid.). Moreover, another paper that does not solely focus on energy prices but other factors that could impact agricultural and food prices is (Gilbert, 2010). According to the author, especially agricultural price booms are explained in a better way by common factors than by market-specific factors, for instance in the form of supply shocks. This is conceptually contrary to the view of (Devadoss and Ridley, 2024) and (Zhang *et al.*, 2024) concerning wheat prices and oil prices during and before the invasion of Ukraine from Russia in 2022, respectively. That is since the latter papers suggest that the war in Ukraine and the resulting supply shocks had indeed an impact on the prices of wheat and oil. The results thus show a significant one-way causality between the war in Ukraine initiated by Russia and crude-oil prices (ibid.).

The GC, that is the granger causality test, is also used in (Derindag *et al.*, 2023). The general model is often used in time-series analysis that use past data of one variable to predict the outcome of another variable (Eric, 2021). It is often used in combination with

a Vector Autoregressive model. The latter is often used as time-series method, especially when looking for the influence of lags of the endogenous variables on themselves, which is called autoregression and all other endogenous variables as well. This means, that instead of checking for significant causal influences of independent variables on the dependent variables, every variable is treated as an independent variable and dependent variable at the same time (Durlauf and Blume, 2010). More on this relationship is provided in the methods section. The general thinking behind this model follows the idea that all variables in the economy have potentially an impact on all other variables. Or as (Leucci *et al.*, 2014) put it: “Economic variables often appear to be self-correlated and cross-correlated for several time lags.”

In contrast to the previous papers (Kirikkaleli and Darbaz, 2021) also analyzed the 2008 worldwide food price rises, but used different methods than the beforementioned GC method in order to check for causal relationships in a bivariate variable context. Instead, the Toda-Yamamoto causality has been used which is according to authors an excellent method for non-stationary data or data that is not co-integrated since it does not require both of these preconditions unlike Granger Causality tests, that requires at least the stationarity condition fulfilled. (*ibid.*) The results demonstrate that there is a causal bidirectional relationship between the “energy price index and food price indexes (in the form of grains, other food, and oils) at different frequencies” (Kirikkaleli and Darbaz, 2021, p. 1). Besides, the tests showed that the energy price changes caused the oil and other food price changes at a 5% significance level. Data were obtained from the world bank and therefore the context of the indices used for energy and food prices is worldwide. The energy price index thus has the advantage compared to solely using crude oil because it consists of a wider range of energy prices, such as coal, crude oil and natural gas, although crude oil prices still represent the biggest overall share with 84.6% (*ibid.*). “However, there is no causality from the energy price index to the grains price index.” (Kirikkaleli and Darbaz, 2021, p. 5) Nevertheless, the Toda-Yamamoto and Fourier Toda-Yamamoto tests both show a bidirectional causal relationship between energy price index and the other food price indices analyzed such as the Grains and Other Food Index at a 5% significance level.

(Roman, Górecka and Domagała, 2020) carried out a very similar research study as the study in Section 3–5. The authors analyze the influence of crude oil prices on several food price indices such as dairy, meat, oils, cereals, and sugar. To conduct their research study,

they use a unit root test, specifically the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)-test to check for stationarity of the variables (ibid.). They use a VAR-model and check for co-integration as well in order to additionally use a VECM-model (Vector Error Correction Model). With these methods they are using very similar data and methods as this empirical study does, as can be seen in Section 3. In addition, they use logarithmic prices in first differences $I(1)$. They focused on the time-period from 1990 to 2020 in a monthly format. Furthermore, the timeframe is put into two subperiods. The first is from 1990 – 2005 and the second from 2006 – 2020. The results show, that in the second period “a moderate correlation occurred between crude oil, and food, cereal, and oil prices.” (ibid., p. 8). It is noteworthy, that the data are put into first order difference variables, except for sugar for the full period (ibid.). This means, that the variables were not stationary, even though they were already put into a logarithmic form, due to a trend or seasonality. Therefore, the first difference had to be created for all variables. After identifying stationarity by using the ADF test, the variables were checked for cointegration using a Johanson integration test. Without explaining the models in detail, the next step was to test the VAR model and VECM model, respectively. Afterwards the Granger Causality has been applied to test the cause-effect relations of all variable pairs with the H_0 hypothesis being that the crude oil prices do not granger cause the respective food price indices. The results reveal long-term (causal) relationships between crude oil and meat prices, while linkages of crude oil and food, cereal, and oil prices in the short-term. Interestingly, the linkages analyzed were increasing for the later period between 2006 until 2020, which is a similar results as (Alom, F., Ward, B.D., & Hu, B., 2011) found for their second period analyzed from 2002 – 2010.

What is more, (Hussain, N. E., Shaari, M. S., & Abdullah, D. N. C., 2018) analyzed diesel and petrol prices (RON 95 and RON 97) on food prices in Malaysia over the period of January 2010 until November 2015. This marks thus the first paper to be introduced, which uses diesel and petrol prices as energy prices in the food price VAR-model context. This proves that similar studies on diesel prices and food prices have been conducted in the past. They used an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) as their method, which is as the name indicates another autoregressive method, that uses lags but is characterized as a univariate model with one dependent variable and several independent variables. The results suggest that diesel prices can trigger a long-run significant causal influence on food price inflation for Malaysia and the time analyzed, while both petrol and diesel prices

show no significant influence in the short-term (ibid.). Another interesting finding by the authors is that: “[...] Oil is not the main input in the industrial sector only but also in the agricultural sector.” (Hussain, N. E., Shaari, M. S., & Abdullah, D. N. C., 2018, p. 28). This insight further suggests using crude-oil based prices such as diesel or petrol as an energy variable for the empirical study.

In this context also (Kristoufek, Janda and Zilberman, 2014) look at mutual responsiveness of fuels such as diesel, petrol and biofuels with their related commodities such as corn and sugarcane: For instance, biodiesel is linked to soybeans. German diesel and ethanol are linked to corn, sugarcane and US gasoline. Further, ethanol and biodiesel show linkages to their production factors that are e.g. soybeans and corn. This linkage will be particularly important when it comes to the influence in the results part in the direction of Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereal prices respectively since these products are used in the production of biofuels (ibid.). Besides, the mutual linkages of the significant pairs mentioned above increased during the food crisis of 2007 and 2008, which strengthens the influence that the primary products have on final fuel products.

Finally, a study that investigates the influence of diesel prices on several food categories along the value chain is presented for the region of Sao Paulo using a VECM model (vector error correction model) that is basically a VAR model that is used if the data is non-stationary but is cointegrated (Zingbagba, Nunes and Fadairo, 2020). The results of the GC test reveal that producer prices are not affected by diesel prices for Sao Paulo and the time frame covered. However, the diesel price granger causes the egg prices of retail markets. Moreover, if food prices to diesel price shocks are observed, the results of both the upstream and downstream for eggs and dairy products are having a positive response, while the opposite is the case for the fat and meat markets, although an initial positive shock of producer prices of meat can also be registered.

Table 1. Overview of previous studies and results

Authors, Year	Methods	Data Source	Time/ Geographical Coverage	Results
Kirikkaleli and Darbaz (2021)	Toda-Yamamoto causality test	World Bank Commodity Prices	Jan. 1980 – Jan. 2019; Worldwide	Significance for all food prices for TY and Fourier TY unless for the grains price index
Roman, Górecka and Domagała (2020)	VAR + VECM + ADF test	No Data source is given here	Jan. 1990 – December 2020; Geography not named	Long-term relationships between crude oil prices and Meat; Short term: Food, cereal and oil prices all significant with crude oil prices
Derindag et al. (2023)	Granger Causality in Quantiles; Wavelet Coherence; QQ Regression	Bloomberg (2021); CBRT (2021) for interest rates and local food prices	January 1999 – August 2022; India	High significance on 5% significance level of 9 independent parameters on food prices
Ma, Xu and Dong (2015)	Granger Causality; Johansson Co-Integration test	US Energy Information Administration (EIA) for crude oil prices; Central Bank of China for Exchange rates	Weekly from June 2002 – August 2013; China	Exchange rate of RMB and Dollar granger causes the prices of soybean
Hussein et. al (2018)	ARDL	“Secondary data source” – not specified by authors	Jan. 2010 – November 2015; Malaysia	Diesel long-term influence on food products; petrol and diesel short-term – no influence
Alom, F. et. al (2011)	VAR and GARCH-family Models	DataStream	Daily from 2 January 1995 to 30 April 2010; Australia, New Zealand, South Korea, Singapore, Hong Kong, Taiwan, India and Thailand	Different magnitudes of influence of energy prices for different countries; mostly short-term significant impact and period from 2002 – 2010 increasing significance
(Kristoufek, Janda and Zilberman, 2014)06.04.25 01:40:00	Value at risk VAR		November 24th, 2003 – February 28th, 2011, in weekly format	Mutual results of commodity prices and bio-fuels such as biodiesel and ethanol

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(Zingbagba, Nunes and Fadairo, 2020)	VECM and Johansson integration test and Granger Causality	Two Data sources: National Agency of Petroleum, Natural Gas and Biofuels (ANP) for DIESEL + The Instituto de Economica Agricola and the Institute of Economic Research Foundation (FIPE) for FOOD Products	July 2001 – December 2013, Sao Paulo (Brazil)	No significant linkages found between the diesel price and producer prices, for retail prices only eggs show that they are granger caused by diesel prices.
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Sources: Depending on study, sources are stated on left hand side of the table. Table created by the author.

3 METHODOLOGY AND DATA

In this section, an overview of the data collection procedure and methods used is given. At first, the research questions are stated and the reason why they have been chosen is elaborated. Secondly, the data collection sources used in the study are explained and listed. Third and finally, all empirical methods used for the empirical study are named and explained in detail.

3.1 Hypothesis

The empirical study is subdivided into three different research parts: Firstly, a bivariate VAR-analysis is carried out, that checks for the influence of a self-created National Austrian Diesel Gross Price Index on all ACP and HICP food price indices, plus the one PPI for food products. Secondly, a VAR-analysis is performed for all indices along the value chain for all four product-groups without any the energy index included in the analysis. The reason to conduct this VAR estimation without energy prices, is to see whether the indices along the value chain have an influence on each other, given the optimal respective lags. Third and lastly, the two approaches are combined, to check for an influence of the diesel prices for all food price indices along the value chain and product groups chosen. It is expected that the linkages between diesel prices and the different food price indices are roughly the same here, as for the bivariate VAR-models. This is the last estimation is carried out for all four product groups separately, resulting in four VAR-estimations. Therefore, in total nine bivariate estimations were conducted, and four estimations without the energy index, and four estimations with the energy index, which makes a total of 17 estimations performed. The outputs for all estimations carried out can be seen in the Appendix Section in Table 11.

The following research hypotheses are referring to the bivariate approach as well as the estimations along the value chain:

- 1. There is a positive causal relationship identified using the GC-test between the Austrian Gross Diesel Price Index from January 2005 until March 2024 and four different food indices along the value chain from Austria.*
- 2. The relationship of diesel prices on the four different ACP indices is stronger than on the HICP indices for the respective product groups, since*

diesel prices are used extensively in agricultural production and transportation processes (Beerge and Devarmani, 2024).

3. There is a causal relationship between the ACP, HICP and IPI (plus for all food products combined PPI index), such that the ACP granger causes the HICP with a positive coefficient since it is the first step along the value chain. Moreover, the IPI index is granger causing both ACP and HICP since product agricultural and consumer products are included in this index alike and the IPI represents an exogenous influence that affects the whole value chain.

This implies for instance that diesel prices have a larger influence on agricultural prices than the consumer prices of food products, since diesel prices are used extensively in agricultural farming for farming equipment such as mowers and tractors (Beerge and Devarmani, 2024). In the US rates about 75% of all farming equipment is powered by diesel, used for 90% of the transporting for farming products (ibid.). However, since diesel prices are mostly influenced by crude oil, since crude oil represents the main ingredient for the production of diesel, the diesel price is expected to influence also the further steps along the value chain (U.S. Energy Information Administration, 2024). Hence, an influence on the HICP is hypothesized as well. This relationship is also elaborated on in the next paragraph, where all variables used are explained. The third hypothesis implies that for instance agricultural prices or producer price indices influence price indices in the next step along the value chain and ultimately consumer prices in the end. Moreover, to answer the respective research questions, a particular dataset and method has been used. These are explained in the following two sub-parts.

3.2 Data

The timeframe which has been chosen for the empirical study are monthly data that have been collected from January 2005 until August of 2024. This timeframe has on the one hand been chosen, since it includes recent events such as the Covid-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine and Russia, beginning in February of 2022, and it begins even before the food price crises of 2008. On the other hand, data of prices of agricultural products along the value chain from the BAB, that were originally published by the EU's food price monitoring tool, were only available since January 2005 (BAB, 2024; Eurostat, 2025). The reason to stop data collection in the month of March 2024 was that the ACP was only available until that month.

Since the data for diesel prices were only available in raw form and every other variable was available in index form, for diesel prices an index has been created. In addition, Indices are a good measure to unify variables and therefore they are better comparable in the final results (Federal Reserve Bank of Dallas, 2024). “They also allow for comparison of variables with different magnitudes” (Federal Reserve Bank of Dallas, 2024), as was the case for the different steps along the value chain. Another reason to use indices was to reduce the effect of possible collinearity issues in STATA, as will be seen in the main explanatory variables Section.

Usually, food price indices are created by using either a Laspeyres, Paasche or Fisher Price Index (Schäfer and European Commission, 2008, p. 18-19). This implies that prices as well as amounts of the respective goods included in the index are available. Here, however only the price is available, since the index has been created for just one specific product. Therefore, a simple one product chain price index has been created in Excel by the author. This effectively means that “[...] the base period is moved forward by one every period”. (Schäfer and European Commission, 2008, p.19)

$$\sum_{i=1}^T T_i = \left(\frac{T_i}{T_{i-1}}\right) * 100 \quad (1)$$

As can be seen in (1) the price for the base period *in i* is divided by the price *in i-1* times 100 while the base period moves forward by one for every period.

Additionally, the diesel prices were only available – at least to the authors knowledge – in weekly format: This was the case for the weekly oil bulletin from the EU (European Commission, 2024; Eurostat, 2025). Therefore, these average prices for every week or month respectively have been calculated in Microsoft Excel by taking the sum of the respective weekly prices per month and dividing it by the number of weeks that the specific month had, when the prices were raised. All the other data sources were already downloaded on the respective websites in monthly index format.

The advantage of the chosen data-sources was for instance, that the data were entirely available for every data point. This in turn guaranteed a better statistical fit of the model, providing that all datapoints are without errors or noise (Moffat and Akpan, 2019). This will be further discussed in the Discussion part, but it is worth mentioning here that nowadays in an economic empirical analysis “[...] the data almost always contains a stochastic component. In everyday language, there is noise in the data.” (Hey, 2005, p.325)

The following Table shows all data sources being used in the quantitative research.

Table 2: All different data sources used for the empirical study

Institution	Data Collection Period	Unit
European Commission - Weekly oil bulletin ²	January 2005 – March 2024	Diesel prices weekly in raw form per 1l converted into Index-form
BAB – Bundesanstalt für Ag- rarwirtschaft und Bergbauern- fragen ³	January 2010 – March 2024	Food Price Indices
Eurostat ⁴	January 2005 – March 2024	Food Price Indices

Sources: Stated below.

A brief overview about the data collection procedure of the respective institutions stated above is given in the following:

Outcome Variables

The outcome variables or dependent variables are all gathered from one source. That is the Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen (BAB, 2024). These prices are all food or agricultural price indices since the study revolves around the influence of energy prices on food price indices in Austria.

The BAB created a pricing portal together with the Österreichische Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung (WIFO), Agrarmarkt Austria (AMA) as well as the Landwirtschaftskammern (LK) Österreich, Niederösterreich and Steiermark (ibid.). This pricing portal has been published in the framework of the ROBVEK-project (Sinabell, 2023), which is concerned about robust supply chains in the agricultural and food industry in Austria. Before the creation of the pricing portal data prices and indices along the value chain were only available via different sources such as the AMA or Landwirtschaftskammern or even

² (European Commission, 2024) Prices for diesel were taken from the weekly oil bulletin

³ (BAB, 2024) All food and agricultural price indices were taken from the BAB from 2010 – 2024 see Table 2

⁴ (Eurostat, 2025) Original Data source for BAB available from 2005 – 2024, therefore data from January of 2005 until December of 2009 has been obtained from the Eurostat website.

only in print format (ibid.) and separately for every product group. The creation of a pricing portal, also for specific product prices along the value chain, has been very helpful because of the need for transparent prices for farmers and participants of the value chain. Moreover, operating resources used during the production process have been added in the agricultural pricing portal for more transparent price reporting access (BAB, 2024). Therefore, the price portal was very helpful for this study. Originally, the price indices were published by the European Commission (Eurostat, 2025), and for the period between January 2005 and December 2010 the data was only published on the Eurostat website and not on the pricing portal. Thus, prices for this specific time-period were gathered from Eurostat and not from the pricing portal of the BAB.

All 13 food price indices along the value chain were already published in index format, set to 100 in the year 2015 and follow four product-groups along the value chain. These product-groups are Bread & Cereal products, Meat products, Food Products in general, that includes all Food Price Categories combined of the Food Price Monitoring Portal of the EU and Oils and Fats (ibid.) Which specific products are included in the respective groups depends on the steps along the value chain. For instance, Oils & Fats both have oils seeds, oleaginous fruits and their seeds included within the ACP for Austria (Eurostat metadata, 2025). Likewise, Bread & Cereal products have cereal seeds included in the ACP (ibid.). Furthermore, it is important to note, that the European Consumer Price Index (CPI) uses certain product codes for different consumer products. For instance, Oils and Fats are specified as CP0115 and include edible fats and oils and oil bearing crops. (European Commission. Joint Research Centre. Institute for Prospective Technological Studies, 2010, p. 19) Next to that, Bread and Cereals (CP 0111) contain all cereal products such as Flour and other grain mill products. Thirdly, Meat with COICOP code, that is Classification of Individual Consumption by Purpose, CP0112 and includes all meats, such as pork, beef and poultry and miscellaneous livestock such as mutton or goat and other meat (ibid.). Finally, food products (CP011) combine all other product groups with relative weighting of the respective sub-food categories.

Moreover, food products were even available in domestic producer price index form (PPI_d), which results in four price indices along the value chain for food products. It is noteworthy that the PPI_d is “[...] a business-cycle indicator showing the development of transaction prices for the monthly industrial output of economic activities. The domestic

producer price index measures the gross monthly change in the trading price of manufactured products.” (Eurostat metadata, 2025) This means that the producer price is already referring to a manufactured product and not a raw product as the ACP.

The other three steps along the value chain were the agricultural price index (ACP), the harmonized index of consumer prices (HICP) as well as “the import price index (IPI) based on unit values from international trade in goods statistics” (Eurostat metadata, 2025). This index consists of all goods that add or subtract from the stock of material resources entering Austrian economic territory (imports) – including goods for processing. In general, it is important to note here that the data is not seasonally adjusted or is at least not referring to seasonal adjustment, except for the IPI index (ibid.). Seasonality is especially important for agricultural price reporting when reported monthly, since certain products are only harvested once a year and therefore monthly prices fluctuate strongly over the course of one year (ibid.). Although the IPI does not measure prices originally coming from Austrian products directly, it can be considered a step along the value chain of food prices and therefore is included in the study and is particularly important when analyzing a potential significant influence along the value chain. However, it is important to note here that wholesale prices are not included in the study and therefore an important step along the value chain is missing in the analysis. The reason for this is as has been mentioned in the introduction, that these price indices were not published in the EU food price monitoring tool, and were therefore not part of the BABs published prices and indices or also not found anywhere else for Austria. (BAB, 2024; Eurostat, 2025).

Main Explanatory Variable – Diesel gross price index for Austria

Although technically, all indices used in this study are outcome or dependent variables, the following is labeled as the main explanatory variable since it is the only energy price being used in the model and therefore its influence on the other endogenous variables is the main focus point of the study. From a statistical standpoint, in a VAR-framework all variables are used as a dependent and independent variables at the same time. For the diesel price to be homogeneous in terms of units, the diesel gross price was converted into index form because the dependent variables were available in index form only. This had the advantage of being better comparable than raw data, which is often published in different hard to compare units (see 3.2 above). Moreover, since all food price indices were set to 100 at year 2015, the same has been done for January of 2015 for the diesel

price index. Beforehand, the raw data from the EU’s weekly oil bulletin for diesel gross prices had to be converted into monthly format. This has been done by taking the sum of all prices per month and dividing it by the number of weeks that the specific month had. The reason to use diesel prices for the empirical study as the sole energy price variable is twofold: First of all, as can be seen from the literature based on the same topic in 2.3, most papers used crude oil prices as the sole energy price or an energy price index (e.g. Kirikkaleli and Darbaz, 2021). The reason is that energy prices are very strongly influenced by crude oil prices, because crude oil is used as main pre-product for lots of energy sources, like diesel and petrol. Thus, the cost of crude oil was contributing approximately half of the monthly average U.S. retail price for diesel highway fuel (U.S. Energy Information Administration, 2024). Therefore, “changes in the price of crude oil explain 93% of the changes in the price of gasoline” in the US from 2000 until August of 2022 (Iowa Farm Bureau, 2022). While this is only evidence from the U.S., these prices do not change significantly for different regions, since diesel prices are produced in the same way everywhere around the world.

Table 3: Correlations between energy prices in Austria from January 2010 until March 2024

	Petrol Euro95	Heating Oil	Diesel prices	Crude Oil Nominal Brent Austria
Petrol Euro95	1.0000			
Heating Oil	0.8532	1.0000		
Diesel prices	0.9849	0.8746	1.0000	
Crude Oil Nominal Brent Austria	0.9698	0.8791	0.9512	1.0000

Source: created by author in STATA using data from EU weekly oil bulletin and BAB. Similarly, the price changes of crude oil explained approximately 89% of the price changes of diesel fuel for the same period (ibid.). Since lots of similar energy variables showed high correlations also in the Austrian case when compared as can be seen in Table 3 above, such as crude oil nominal brent prices with petrol prices, diesel prices and heating oil, the number of energy variables used in the VAR-model had to be decreased sub-

stantially. This is because of model multicollinearity issues arising when too many variables that are correlated are used in the same regression model, leading to distorted results (Harrell, 2015). Secondly, the decision to use diesel prices was motivated by the fact that generally in the agricultural process diesel is very important. That is because machines in agriculture only work with traditional fuels like diesel or petrol, because electric motors are not strong or efficient and most of all reliant enough to work in agriculture for machineries such as mower threshers or tractors (Beerge and Devarmani, 2024; Eurostat metadata, 2025).

Furthermore, the decision to take either the net diesel or gross diesel price had to be taken. The fact that Austrian diesel fuel prices were used in gross format, is due to the fact that only a small percentage in CO₂ rich diesel-taxes can be reclaimed, and only since 2022 (Parliament Austria, 2024). Nevertheless, agricultural farmers within Austria are released from paying all of the taxes for bio-diesel and other oil related products they buy since the introduction of the “Mineralölsteuergesetz” from 1995 (Bundeskanzleramt Österreich, 1994). For standard diesel or oil prices however, all taxes have to be paid normally and only since recent years are there partial reliefs for farm businesses:

Since 2022 in Austria 7 cents per liter of diesel bought, were paid back for farmers which is called “Agrardiesel-Vergütung” (Parliament Austria, 2024). This means that they are affected by the diesel gross price as well and even more than the net price, since they only get a certain percentage of the whole tax back. All in all, since 2022 20,5 cents could be reclaimed for agricultural enterprises from mineral oil taxes (ibid.). Consequently, the diesel gross price for Austria, as published by the EU weekly oil bulletin and BAB respectively, has been used in the empirical study (BAB, 2024; European Commission, 2024).

For a structural overview, a list of all different variables with sources, and a brief definition is provided below.

Table 4: All variables used in the empirical part with explanation

Variable	Brief Definition	Source
Diesel_Gross_Index	Diesel Gross Index for Austria	EU weekly oil bulletin
BreadCereal_ACP	Agricultural price of Bread & Cereal Products	ROBVEK-Projekt
Meat_products_ACP	Agricultural price of Meat Products	ROBVEK-Projekt
Food_products_ACP	Agricultural price of Food Products	ROBVEK-Projekt
Oils&fats_ACP	Agricultural price of Oils & Fats-Products	ROBVEK-Projekt
BreadCereal_HICP	Harmonized Index of Consumer Prices for	ROBVEK-Projekt
Meat_products_HICP	Harmonized Index of Consumer Prices for	ROBVEK-Projekt
Food_products_HICP	Harmonized Index of Consumer Prices for	ROBVEK-Projekt
Oilsfats_HICP	Harmonized Index of Consumer Prices for	ROBVEK-Projekt
BreadCereal_IPI	Import Price Index for Bread & Cereal	ROBVEK-Projekt
Meat_products_IPI	Import Price Index for Meat Products	ROBVEK-Projekt
Food_products_IPI	Import Price Index for Food Products	ROBVEK-Projekt
Oil_&_fats_IPI	Import Price Index for Oil & Fat Products	ROBVEK-Projekt
Food_products_ppi	Producer Price Index for Food Products	ROBVEK-Projekt

Source: Data based on price portal of (BAB, 2024) and (European Commission, 2024; Eurostat, 2025), Table created by author in STATA.

3.3 Empirical Methods

Figure 4: All Four Food HICP in Austria from January 2005 until 2024

Source: Authors creation with STATA. Data based on price portal of (BAB, 2024).

As a first presentation of the data graphically, Figure 4 shows all four food product indices combined. Especially striking to see here is the high rise of all price indices for food products beginning roughly in 2020. Overall, an upward trend is clearly visible for all food price indices. In addition, it is interesting to see that the ACP has a higher volatility than the other indices, implying also a higher standard error, which can be seen in Table 6. Further, since 2020 and especially approximately in 2022, all prices reached their respective peaks. As has been described earlier, possible reasons for that are the Covid-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine caused by Russia (Devadoss and Ridley, 2024; Zhang *et al.*, 2024).

Moreover, what can be seen in the both Figures are the first peaks before the 2022 peaks occurring approximately around the year 2008. Especially, the ACP peak is visible, that was only topped around the year 2021/2022. During the whole period of almost 19 years in relative terms this price index almost doubled until 2022 but afterwards fell again.

Figure 5: ACP, IPI and HICP for food products as indices and diesel gross price Index of Austria

Sources: created in STATA using (BAB, 2024) data.

As you can see in Figure 5, the ACP for food products and the Diesel Gross Price Index tend to correlate. A possible reason for that could be the association between the two variables explained in the data description section before. For the other indices, the differences are not that clearly visible, so it's difficult to judge them. What is also visible is that the diesel prices, although being in index format are much more volatile. The reason for this can be explained due to the fact, that diesel is the only product in the index and not several products as e.g. in the HICP are included in the index, which reduces volatility in the index (DESTATIS - Statistisches Bundesamt, 2022).

In order to validate or invalidate the research questions stated in 3.1 a multivariate time-series regression method has been used. Since in the study more than one dependent variable has been used, a nonlinear multivariate regression method for time-series analysis has been chosen. The main method for the empirical study was a *VAR-model (vector autoregressive model)*.

A simple VAR-model in OLS (ordinary least squares) form with two endogenous variables is given below (Levendis, 2023, p. 266):

$$X_t = \alpha_x + \beta_{x,1} X_{t-1} + \beta_{y,2} Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_{x,t} \quad (2)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_y + \beta_{x,1} X_{t-1} + \beta_{y,2} Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_{y,t} \quad (3)$$

α_x and α_y are constant terms; $\beta_{x,1}$ is the first coefficient matrix of the first endogenous variable X_{t-1} and $\beta_{y,2}$ is the second coefficient of the second endogenous variable and Y_{t-1} is the second endogenous variable. $\epsilon_{x,t}$ is the white noise or error vector that is independently and identically distributed, in the optimal case, with no autocorrelation of the errors. Generally, white noise implies that “[...] there is no leftover structure to the data that we have neglected to model.” (Levendis, 2023, p.49)

The latter assumption is especially important for testing the fit or quality of the model, which will be explained further in the Discussion Section in Part 5.

If a VAR-model is used that has more than two endogenous variables, the number of vectors for coefficients and variables increases accordingly. Similarly, if the number of lags increases, the variables and vectors are added for $t - i$ periods, where i denotes the number of lags (ibid.)

This is the basic model for the empirical study. In this case, the lag is one for the variables X_t and Y_t respectively. It is the simplest VAR-Model with one lag and two variables (Levendis, 2023). Since VAR-Models include an autoregressive part, that also tests if the variable is significant on the specific variable itself as well as all other endogenous variables for different lags, it was seen as an appropriate model for this study’s purposes. That is, since in the study possible influences in the form of causal relationships between agricultural or food prices along the value chain and specific Austrian energy prices are analyzed. As the literature review showed, especially the agricultural commodities and food market is very complex in terms of dynamics, which is suggesting a multivariate approach as an empirical method (Leucci *et al.*, 2014). Further, as already established in general within economic models all variables have potentially an influence on every other variable (ibid.).

The inclusion of different lags means that for instance at a lag of one, the influence of the variable on itself and other endogenous variables will be checked for the period $t - 1$. Normally, the default option is taking both lags 1 2, at least in the statistical software STATA, which was being used for the empirical study (StataCorp, 2021, p.773). The interpretation of this simple VAR-model is shown in (2) and (3) is as follows: The regression is run for one lag of the same variable and one lag of the other endogenous variable. Let X_t be the harmonized consumer price index (HICP) for all food products in Austria and Y_t be crude oil prices in Austria. Therefore, the regression is done for the first lag of the HICP of food products themselves and on the first lag of crude oil prices, respectively. Thus, the VAR model checks if a significant influence is found of the HICP variables of the past period on the present period of Diesel Price Index and vice versa. For this reason, including a trend variable of simply a progressive number sequence ($X = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, \dots$) as an exogenous independent variable is a commonly used option for finding out whether a statistically significant trend is present in the model. As (Liang and Li, 2012) show this is especially important in economic contexts, since trends are occurring very often in economics. Further, “This trend variable can serve as a proxy for a variable that affects the dependent variable and is not directly observable.” (econometrics.com, 2025) Moreover, typically a VAR-model first requires a unit root test or stationarity test to proceed with the calculation of the VAR-model itself to check for stationarity of the data. In general stationarity is present if the mean, variance and autocorrelation of a variable doesn’t change or “remains unwavering” over time (Tate. A, 2023). This test is very important since, most time-series analysis methods rely on stationarity as a precondition – this is also true for the VAR-model (ibid.) One test to check for stationarity in time-series data is the *Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF-test)*. The ADF-test checks, if a time series has a unit root (Guo, 2023), which basically means that the mean and variance of the series is not constant over time. Table 10 in the appendix section displays all results of the ADF-test for both the level form and the first difference form for all variables used. There were no extra lags chosen for the ADF-test, since the data were not used in a VAR model yet. Although an extra option for including the respective covariates of the lags to the ADF-test exists, this option has not been included in the test, and the default option was chosen for all variables. The number of observations were in the level case 230 and in the first difference case 229 respectively for every variable. As can be seen from Table 10 in the Appendix section, the level results show no significance for p-values ranging

from an α -level of 1 – 10%. This means that the H_0 which states that the variables have a unit root or are not stationary cannot be rejected. As a result, the variables are not stationary. Thus, the variables had to be transformed into first difference form of the variables in t and $t-1$ respective values. As can be seen in Table 10, the results of the ADF-test are significant on a 1% level for all variables, which means the Null hypothesis, that the variables have a unit root, can be rejected. Therefore, the first differences can be used for the VAR-model.

Moreover, following (Lütkepohl, 2005, p.70) the total amount of parameters estimated in a VAR-model are:

$$k(k \times p) + k \quad (4)$$

Where k denotes the number of variables used and p the number of lags, the k term results from the constant estimated for each variable used. This condition will be important when considering how many lags can be chosen in the VAR-Estimations.

Furthermore, some additional tests were included after the VAR-analysis, such as *Granger Causality Wald test* (see also Granger, 1969) to identify if there is a causal relationship in the variables found and which direction this relationship has. According to (Obadi, S., Korcek, M., 2014) the equations for GC can be written as the following:

$$X_t = \alpha_1 + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j X_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_j Y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (5)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_2 + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma_j Y_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^m \delta_j X_{t-j} + \varepsilon_{2t} \quad (6)$$

Here “ m is the maximum number of lagged observations included in the model (the model order), the matrix β , γ , δ , and λ contains the coefficients of the model (i.e., the contributions of each lagged observation to the predicted values of X_t and Y_t , α_1 , α_2 are constants and ε_{1t} , ε_{2t} are residuals (prediction error terms) for each time series.” (Obadi, S., Korcek, M., 2014, p. 420).

Generally, the Granger Causality Wald tests, tests the following hypothesis:

The H_0 : $\lambda_j = 0$ for all j . This means if interpreted that the past values of Y_t have no influence on X_t . Consequently, the H_1 hypothesis states that the past values of λ_j are significantly different from 0 ($\neq 0$), which implies that the past values of Y_t improve the prediction of X_t . This in turn means that Y_t is granger causing X_t . The same concept can be applied for X_t on Y_t for the coefficient δ_j in equation (6).

In fact, as (Pasrun A., Rosnawintang R., La Ode S., La Tondi, La Ode Arsad S., 2018) pointed out various literature sources in the field that performed a test of causality after conducting a VAR-Analysis.

Furthermore, the direction of the causality can already be seen in the p-value results of the respective variables of the VAR estimation model (ibid.). “Thus, this Granger causality test is an advanced test to reinforce the test results of the coefficient significance of the endogenous variables” (Pasrun A., Rosnawintang R., La Ode S., La Tondi, La Ode Arsad S.93, 2018). Essentially, the GC checks whether one variable granger causes another. The H_0 : “diesel gross price index does not granger cause the respective food price index” is rejected if the GC Wald-tests’ p-value is below the 5% or 10% threshold depending on what α is chosen.⁵ Thus, if the H_0 is rejected the diesel gross price index has a causal influence on the respective food price index in the amount of the coefficient.

In summary, three concepts were used to answer the research questions stated in the methods part. The first one was to analyze only two variables – one energy variable and one HICP or ACP of the four food product categories chosen. For energy variables the gross diesel price seemed to be the most suitable for the endeavor as described in the data section (3.1.)

Following most literature from 2.3 a bivariate approach made sense given that the total amount of observations was about 230 for the VAR(1) model, meaning for the first difference I(1) variables. And by following (Harrell , 2015) per parameter estimated there should be at least 10 to 15 observations for a stable regression model. Following this rule, at the most 23 parameters could be estimated per model, resulting in 10 observations per parameter estimated. As the ACP marks the first stage within the value chain and hence no other energy variable should be causing an impact in this first step, the diesel price is expected to have the higher impact on the ACP than on the final step in the value chain, the HICP.

The second approach was to see whether any significant influences could be identified using only three or in the case of food products four steps or indices along the value chain without diesel index added to the model and using only one optimal lag in order to comply with equation (4).

⁵ For a detailed version of the model, please see (Granger, 1969).

Thirdly, the diesel gross price index has been added to the food price indices along the value chain of the previous model, again with only one lag. Thus, the reason to only use one lag was due to the study being limited on the number of observations and parameters. The next step was trying to identify the best or optimal lag number(s) for the three studies, separately. This final step before presenting the results is closely linked to the goodness or fit of the model, since the lag-order chosen determines if autocorrelation or normality of the residuals of the model is given or not. Consequently, this step was crucial in ensuring that the model was representing the actual data and in the next step testing the models' durability. This endeavor has been carried out in a twofold manner: Firstly, the AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) (Akaike, 1974), the HQIC (Hannan Quinn Information Criterion) and SBIC (Schwarz Bayesian Information Criterion) or BIC, that is Bayesian Information Criterion have been used to find out the optimal lag. All these parameters represent criteria based on the log-likelihood of the model and are used in different contexts, depending on the complexity of the model (Clement, L., no date).

The second step was to check whether the residuals were autocorrelated at the optimal lag numbers, as this is the most important factor when it comes to model adequacy for residuals not being autocorrelated in an autocorrelated model (Moffat and Akpan, 2019) as will be seen in the Discussion Section of the results. For this purpose, a Lagrange Multiplier test (LM-test) has been conducted, which will be explained in the discussion part. For the bivariate part, if the LM-test showed that the variables or rather the residuals were autocorrelated at the optimal lag number, another lag between 1 and 10 has been applied that was either result from the other two of the three criteria of AIC, SBIC and HQIC chosen or was close to the first optimal lag-number identified.

4 RESULTS

The following section is divided into five different parts and presents the results from all VAR-estimations and granger causality tests performed. The interpretation of these results will be set out and further elaborated on in the discussion section. The first results show a simple OLS-regression and a descriptive statistics part. For the regression the four different HICPs of the respective food product groups are chosen as dependent variables and the diesel gross price index has been selected as independent variable. The statistics section shows general statistics such as mean, standard deviation, min and max of the respective variables. Following this section, the results of the nine bivariate VAR-estimation models are shown. Third, the VAR-models along the value chain including the diesel price index and without the diesel price index.

4.1 Descriptive associations and simple OLS regression

It can be assumed when comparing Figure 6 and 7, that food price indices have a lag or delay compared to energy price indices and the peak prices of the whole period from 2005 to 2024 is roughly occurring in 2022. This is another indicator that a VAR-model is reasonable to use, since the model is based on lags and can be used in a multivariate context. Besides, Figure 7 shows crude oil-based product prices without including taxes. The high correlations of similar fuels or crude oil-based products, such as diesel or petrol are clearly visible here. This relationship can also be observed in Table 6. Moreover, the graphical representation suggests further that including all energy prices into the VAR-model would lead to multicollinearity and the regression performed is not reliable anymore (The Pennsylvania State University, 2025), because of all the variables being correlated by over 90 percentage points. For further information about optimal fit of the data and optimal parameter amount chosen, see (Harrell, 2015).

Before the actual VAR-Models are performed a simple linear regression with one dependent variable and one independent variable is performed to see whether there is a significant influence of energy prices, specifically diesel prices on the harmonized indices of consumer prices (HICP) without any lag and other exogenous variables, such as trends. The results are shown in the following table:

Table 5: Influence of Diesel Price Index on HICP Price Indices via simple OLS regression in STATA from January 2005 until March 2024

Variable (HICP)	R-Squared	Adj R-Squared	Coefficient	p-Value	Observations
Food Products	0.4789	0.4766	0.4652434	0.000	231
Meat Products	0.4749	0.4726	0.5154371	0.000	231
Bread & Cereal	0.4662	0.4639	0.497864	0.000	231
Oils & Fats	0.5193	0.5172	0.6843189	0.000	231

Source: created by author with data from (BAB, 2024; Eurostat, 2025)

The Harmonized Index of Consumer Prices has been chosen since it represents the price index that has had the most steps along the value chain from the three or four chosen price indices. The output clearly shows that in a model only with diesel prices as independent variable there is a significant influence from diesel prices on all four products groups' HICPs. Moreover, the R-Squared is nearly 50 percent for all product groups, and similarly the Adjusted R-Squared.

Figure 6: HICP Indices for Food Products from 2020 – 2024

Source: created by author using (BAB, 2024).

Figure 7: Energy Indices in Austria from 2020 – 2024

Source: created by author using (BAB, 2024)

Table 6: Descriptive statistics for all variables in first differences:

Variable I(1)	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Diesel Gross Index	230	.328	4.626	-19.342	35.964
Food Products ACP	230	.226	2.279	-7.4	8.6
BreadCereal ACP	230	.132	11.136	-39.8	62.9
Meat ACP	230	.217	1.669	-4.5	7.9
OilsFats ACP	230	.059	4.432	-17.3	19.4
Food Products HICP	230	.254	0.692	-3.89	3.39
BreadCereal HICP	230	.283	0.602	-2.37	2.91
Meat HICP	230	.272	0.998	-4.89	6.14
OilsFats HICP	230	.346	1.566	-5.74	6.78
Food Product ppi	230	.224	0.621	-1	4.1
Food Products IPI	230	.321	1.113	-3	5.4
BreadCereal IPI	230	.31	2.231	-7.7	8
Meat IPI	230	.244	2.524	-5.9	11.6
OilsFats IPI	230	.403	3.492	-11.7	9.5

Source: created by author in STATA.

This means that the estimated parameters in the model explain about 45% of the actual data in a linear OLS-regression model.

4.2 Bivariate VAR-Models for ACP and HICP prices

Table 7: Results of Bivariate VAR-Models for all ACP and HICP prices with GC

<i>Diesel → Food Products ACP:</i> 0.0711** (5); 0.0260 (10) and GC Prob > Chi2: 0.076	<i>Diesel → Food products HICP:</i> 0.0244*** (8); 0.0301*** (9)
<i>Food Products ACP → Diesel:</i> 0.0752 (5); 0.0700 (10)	<i>Food products HICP → Diesel:</i> -0.1198 (8); -1.277*** (9)
<i>Diesel → Bread & Cereal ACP:</i> 0.0193 (5); 0.0712 (10)	<i>Diesel → Bread & Cereal HICP:</i> 0.012 (6); 0.0289*** (10)
<i>Bread & Cereal ACP → Diesel:</i> 0.0827*** (5); 0.0163 (10)	<i>Bread & Cereal HICP → Diesel:</i> -0.2658 (6); -1.8315*** (10)
<i>Diesel → Oils & Fats ACP:</i> -0.0018 (9); -0.0930 (10)	<i>Diesel → Oils & Fats HICP:</i> 0.0552*** (1); 0.0919*** (3);
<i>Oils & Fats ACP → Diesel:</i> -0.2308** (9); 0.2517** (10) and GC Prob > Chi2: 0.062;	<i>Oils & Fats HICP → Diesel:</i> 0.7683*** (1); -0.0280 (3)
<i>Diesel → Meat ACP:</i> 0.0654*** (9); 0.0921*** (10)	<i>Diesel → Meat HICP:</i> 0.0456*** (1); 0.0120 (6)
<i>Meat ACP → Diesel:</i> -0.3416 (9); 0.0942 (10)	<i>Meat HICP → Diesel:</i> 0.1042 (1); -0.4482 (6)
<i>Food Products PPI → Diesel:</i> 1.4006*** (1); -0.2850 (9) and GC Prob > Chi2: 0.028	<i>Diesel → Food Products PPI:</i> 0.0112 (1); 0.01249 (9)

Source: Table created by author in STATA; Coefficients from STATA study, ***, **, *, 1%, 5%, 10% significance using p-value of z-statistics of VAR-estimations.

In table 7 you see all results for the bivariate VAR-estimations and GC-analysis.

Note that → and ← signal the direction of the analyzed linkage and the respective opposite linkage is always presented below. The numbers represent the coefficient term and numbers in parentheses are lag numbers. Note that only coefficients that are marked with

a star are significant. For each test two optimal lag numbers were chosen, although not all are significant. If not marked otherwise the Granger Causality tests' Prob > chi2 matches the p-value of the z-statistic of the VAR-estimations.

In general, the bivariate results that can be seen in Table 8 show a positive significant influence in the form of granger causality for diesel prices on ACP and HICP price indices for all four product groups, except for the PPI of food products, Bread & Cereal ACP, and Oils & Fats ACP: For instance, for Food Products ACP and HICP, even for both lags (8th and 9th) in the latter case. Nonetheless, the coefficient on the ACP is higher and more than double that of both HICP significant coefficients.

The H_0 that has been tested was whether the influence of the gross diesel price index created by the author was not significantly different from zero for the food price indices analyzed or if the H_0 could be rejected, if the p-value was lower than the 10, 5 or 1 percent level resulting in the diesel price granger causing the food products. Moreover, the diesel price index granger causes the ACP of meat prices with a coefficient of 0.0654 for the 9th and 0.092110th lag respectively on a 1% level.

Given the second hypothesis from the methods part, it is interesting to observe that the HICP of all four product-groups is granger caused with a positive coefficient by the diesel price index on the 1% level. That is since, the diesel price index was thought to be influencing the ACP more than the HICP, since diesel plays such an important role for agricultural machinery (Beerge and Devarmani, 2024). That means that the second hypothesis, stated in 3.1 can be rejected according to these results.

While these results confirm the first and main hypothesis, stated in section 3.1, that diesel prices have a causal influence on the food price indices along the value chain for the respective product groups, there are some unexcepted findings as well, when it comes to the opposite effect of the food price indices influencing diesel prices:

Firstly, an unexpected finding can be seen, if we compare the Diesel Prices granger causing the ACP and HICP Meat Products. In these cases, the lags for both indices are higher for the ACP than for the HICP. The same phenomenon can be observed when looking at Oils & Fats ACP and HICP granger causing the Diesel Price Index. This is an unexpected finding, because the ACP is the first step in the value chain of the product groups and thus it was expected that a lower lag would cause diesel prices to have an impact on the ACP than for the last step along the value chain.

Secondly, for Oils & Fats the relationship is even reversed, meaning that not diesel prices have an influence on Oils & Fats but rather the opposite is true for both the ACP and HICP. The same can be said about Bread & Cereal where the linkage can be found in the direction of the seeds (ACP) influencing the diesel gross price index.

However, the influence of the HICP price index on the diesel price index occurs also already after only one lag (see Table 8). When looking at the results for combined food products index, where all registered foods by the EU for Austria are published, the results satisfy the expectations for the most important lag length and sign of the coefficient. The only index where this is not the case was the PPI and the HICP for food products, where the coefficient was approximately 1.400 for the PPI index influencing the diesel price index and not the other way round. This result is contrary concerning the prefix to the influence of the HICP to the diesel price index where the result is negative with a coefficient of -1.277 . These results have in addition the coefficients with the highest magnitude of the whole bivariate analysis, which is surprising since these associations or even causal impacts of food products on the diesel price index were not expected at all in the hypothesis section.

Lastly, the Oils & Fats results for the ACP for the 9th and 10th lag was -0.2308 and 0.2517 , respectively, which is surprising only because of the prefix being the opposite. The interpretations and possible explanations for these results are stated in the discussion section.

4.3 VAR-Models along the value chain without diesel prices

Table 8: Results of VAR-Analysis along the value Chain from Jan. 2005 – Mar. 2024 for all four product groups.

	Food Products ACP	Food Products PPI	Food Products IPI	Food Products HICP
Food Products ACP	0.1311*	0.0366**	0.0320	0.0440**
Food Products PPI	-0.4628*	0.2618***	0.1166	0.1265
Food Products IPI	-0.1121	-0.0395	0.0132	0.0854*
Food Products HICP	-0.5089**	-0.0242	0.0756	0.0232

Source: created in STATA. The horizontal line represents the endogenous variables and the vertical line the exogenous variables for the respective columns of all four tables. Note

that the intersections of the variables with themselves represent the autoregressive component.

Note that the variables at top of the table are the ones that are the endogenous variables and the variables at the left-hand side are the ones that are exogenous with the respective optimal lags. Moreover, for all models but for meat prices a lag of 10 has been found optimal since it was found to be optimal in the AIC analysis. For Meat prices a lag of 5 has been identified as optimal and the residuals were also not autocorrelated as can be seen in Table 12 in the Appendix Section. The food products results are as expected in the hypothesis, with the exception of the PPI index and HICP index having negative prefixes to their respective significant coefficients on the ACP index. The possible explanation and interpretations are given in the discussion part.

Bread & Cereal Indices:

	Bread & Cereal ACP	Bread & Cereal HICP	Bread & Cereal IPI
Bread & Cereal ACP	0.0326	0.0085**	0.0037
Bread & Cereal HICP	-3.1988***	0.2055***	-0.3941
Bread & Cereal IPI	0.0481	0.0481***	-0.0207

Source: created in STATA by author.

In the case of Bread & Cereals it is clearly visible that the HICP, ACP and IPI all have an influence on the HICP of Bread & Cereals itself. The only other significant influence is coming from the HICP on the ACP, which has a negative prefix and with 3.1988 is the highest influence in any VAR-estimation conducted. This essentially means that if the HICP is growing by one point, the ACP is decreasing over three points after 10 lags which means 10 months later. It is also noticeable that the same can be seen for food products, but the coefficient is only -0.5089. An interpretation for this particular linkage is given in the discussion section.

Oils & Fats Indices:

	Oils & Fats ACP	Oils & Fats HICP	Oils & Fats IPI
Oils & Fats ACP	0.3529***	0.0144	-0.0773
Oils & Fats HICP	-0.2782	-0.0940	0.2575*
Oils & Fats IPI	-0.1536**	-0.0445	0.0503

Source: created in STATA by author.

The case of Oils & Fats is a bit different than for Bread & Cereals or Food Products. In this case three relations were significant. One of them is the ACP on the ACP itself, also after 10 lags and with a positive prefix. Another one is the IPI on the ACP: This one has a negative coefficient of 0.1536 on the 5% level. The third relationship is the positive influence of the HICP on the IPI.

Meat Indices (Lag 5):

	Meat ACP	Meat HICP	Meat IPI
Meat ACP	-0.0655	0.1005**	-0.0301
Meat HICP	-0.0269	-0.0018	-0.0906
Meat IPI	-0.0301	-0.0437	0.0602

Source: created in STATA by author.

The only significant influence for the sole VAR model of Meat products is coming from the ACP index on the HICP index. That linkage is at the same time the most important influence which occurred for three out of four food product-groups. Only for Oils & Fats was this linkage not significant. What is also important to note here, is that the influence is positive for all product-groups.

What is also noteworthy from the results without diesel prices along the value chain is that the linkage of HICP on ACP index has for all products a negative sign in front of the coefficient, although only significant for Bread & Cereal and Food Products. Nevertheless, the influence for Bread & Cereal has the highest coefficient with -3.1988. When interpreted this means that a one unit increase of the HICP results after 10 months in over 3 units drop of the ACP.

4.4 VAR-Models along the value chain with diesel prices

Table 9: Results of all food price indices along the value chain with diesel prices included as an endogenous variable from Jan. 2005 – Mar. 2024

Diesel Price Index → Food Products ppi for lag (10)	0.0202**
Diesel Price Index → Bread & Cereal HICP for lag (10)	0.0279***
Diesel Price Index → Meat ACP for lag (10)	0.0885***

Source: Derived from STATA. Created by author.

The results from Table 7 can be categorized into the same framework of the bivariate VAR-analysis, since the Diesel Price Index has a positive influence on the four Food Price Indices except for Oils & Fats. Because of that these results are strengthening the results and first hypothesis from Part 3.1 that the diesel price index has a positive influence on the food price indices. Furthermore, different lags compared to the bivariate analysis have been identified as optimal for the food products PPI – lag 10 instead of lag 1 and lag 9 in the bivariate case, has been identified as the optimal lag.

Thus, the results differ as well: Whereas there has no granger causality been identified for the bivariate model for diesel prices index on food products PPI, in the case for all steps along value chain for food products indices, the diesel price index granger causes the food products PPI with a positive coefficient similar as to the other indices. Hence, only one lag further back, can change the significance of the coefficient and the latter is suddenly relevant. However, note that for the food products along the value chain with diesel price index included in the model, although no trend variable has been added 30 parameters were estimated, which can be seen in the Appendix Section, and this exceeds strictly speaking the threshold of 23 parameters maximally estimated for 230 total observations.

Nevertheless, this strengthens the optimal lag of 10 for the whole VAR-estimations. That is, since lag 10 has been used for 12 models out of 17 models that were in total estimated in the whole empirical study.

Lastly, high influences of autocorrelation have been found in the results of all VAR-models. Consequently, the variables are dependent on their own lags and depend strongly on their past values. – see log-file attached.

5 DISCUSSION

The results identified for the direction of diesel prices influencing food price indices was throughout the whole empirical study as expected from the hypothesis a positive significant influence of diesel prices on ACPs, HICPs for the four product groups analyzed, that are: Bread & Cereal, Meat products, Oils & Fats and all-Food-Products-combined. To begin with, the hypothesis for the respective VAR-models performed are stated. Afterwards the results found in the last section are interpreted.

5.1 Discussion of results

To recapitulate the results, most importantly the first and main hypothesis of the Thesis has been answered to satisfaction. That is, that the diesel price index is granger causing the food and agricultural price indices of most of the product groups observed, except for Food Products PPI and the Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereals ACP.

The second hypothesis has been denied, since the HICP has been influenced more often and with a higher magnitude than the ACP. The third hypothesis can be confirmed if considered in the light of the ACP influencing the HICP except for the Oils & Fats products. However, there were some highly unanticipated results for the HICP influencing the ACP with a negative coefficient. This will be debated at the end of 5.1. Now, the interpretations for all results are demonstrated:

Firstly, the results of the nine bivariate models performed are presented here: When looking at the results from Table 8, the diesel price index shows no GC impact on the producer price index, PPI, of food products, and the Bread & Cereal ACP, and Oils & Fats ACP.

A possible reason for this is that not a lot of farming equipment is needed for the first few steps in the value chain. Intuitively, for Bread & Cereal and Oils & Fats especially there is less equipment and energy needed compared to e.g. meat products, since this index already includes the energy needed for Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereals categories for feeding the animals. Moreover, additional transportation costs are a lot higher, since these animals are very heavy and for maintenance of barns and sheds more energy is needed.

Further, as an example for an interpretation of the findings in words, the following is presented: The optimal lags for the HICP of food products were the 8th and 9th lag meaning the lagged diesel prices for eight and nine months respectively have a causal impact on the current HICP of food products with a positive coefficient. For instance, for the first difference of the HICP of food products an increase of the ninth lag of the first difference

of diesel price index by 1 point, results in the current HICP rising by 0.0301. Note here, that these coefficients might seem small, but the mean of the I(1) variables ranges from 0.059 to 0.403, as can be seen in Table 7.

Secondly, the GC influence of the Diesel Price Index on all HICP indices can be explained by the amount of energy used during the production process for transportation, farming, packaging etc. Since this marks the last step in the value chain diesel and other crude-oil based products have been used during all steps that occurred before. Generally, what is important to note here is that crude oil prices, such as diesel prices are influencing the world economy and crude oil-based products are the most important energy source for both the farming and industrial sector, as has already been described by (Hussain, N. E., Shaari, M. S., & Abdullah, D. N. C., 2018).

Thirdly, there were some unexpected findings in the bivariate VAR-model results: There were higher optimal lags for the granger causing diesel price for ACP (lags of 9 and 10 were found out to be optimal) displayed in the results compared to the HICP indices (the optimal lag was 1) for meat products despite these products being produced earlier in the value chain: One possible explanation for this result is that for the agricultural meat prices, feeding consumer products are needed that are final products were a lot of steps along the value chain took place. Thus, these prices are potentially influencing the ACP of meat products and a lag already included in the price since they are consumer products. The lower lag for the HICP of meat prices could on the other hand be explained by transportation of slaughter-ready cows and other meats and also transportation to the retail stores with diesel vehicles is taking place at the end of the value chain. Hence a low lag of the diesel price index can be explained for the HICP of meat prices.

Another crucial insight that could be seen in the results was that the opposite effect of Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereal products granger causing the diesel price index instead of the ordinary effect vice versa. This can be explained by the Oils & Fats ACP having amongst other products seeds included in the index and some of these seeds can also be used for producing biodiesel, which influences the price of normal crude oil-based diesel (FCIO - Fachverband der Chemischen Industrie Österreichs, 2025). Generally, biodiesel in Austria is produced by either fresh or used animal and vegetable fats (ibid.). This is exactly what the Oils & Fats index consists of (Eurostat metadata, 2025). Therefore, the influence of both the ACP and HICP index on the diesel price index could be resulting from that linkage. Interestingly, Austria produced about 77% of the Biodiesel they used

themselves, which was about 317,900 tons for the year 2022 (FCIO - Fachverband der Chemischen Industrie Österreichs, 2025). Moreover, 17.5% were produced in Austria directly from agricultural production (ibid.). This is why the ACP and also HICP play an important role here. Usually, the most part of biodiesel produced is mixed into normal crude-oil based diesel, as an additive. Nevertheless, in 2022 for instance 28,349 tons were sold as pure biodiesel product or diesel with more than 50% admixture of biodiesel (ibid.). Therefore, the product can also serve as a competitive product to normal diesel fuel. This can explain the negative sign in front of some of the coefficients of Oils & Fats but also Bread & Cereals. Further, this important insight partially explains why the Bread & Cereal and Oils & Fats ACP are not granger caused by the Diesel Price Index: Since they are themselves granger causing the Diesel Price.

Likewise, a surprising and not anticipated result, were the different prefixes of the significant coefficients for Oils & Fats ACP on the Diesel Price Index. A reasonable explanation for this could be the prices of Oils & Fats fluctuating between the 9th and 10th lag or month. In the 9th month prices could have been decreasing at the time while one month later (the 10th lag) they were increasing again, but both months have a significant influence on the Diesel Gross Price.

A further finding that was not anticipated were the optimal lags for Oils & Fats HICP granger causing the diesel price index being higher than for the ACP. While this might seem counterintuitive at first, it makes sense when accounted for the fact that in this case not only the production process of food products is looked at, but rather the other way round and the consumer products are used to produce diesel in the form of biodiesel as an additive to the normal crude oil-based diesel. Therefore, the shorter lag can be explained by this association, since the already produced oils are used for biodiesel as well as seeds (FCIO - Fachverband der Chemischen Industrie Österreichs, 2025).

Lastly, one possible interpretation for the Food products PPI granger causing the diesel price index positively with a coefficient of 1.400 may also be caused by the biodiesel association since these product groups are a part of the overall food products category.

All in all, the bivariate results can therefore be explained reasonably.

Now that the results of all bivariate VAR-Models have been discussed, the results that are noteworthy along the value chain are discussed as well:

It was suspected given the third hypothesis from the methods section in 3.1. that the IPI is granger causing the ACP and HICP. This was the case for the Bread & Cereals HICP (coefficient of 0.0481) and Food Products HICP (with a coefficient of 0.0854) with a positive coefficient and for Oils & Fats ACP with a negative coefficient. Since the Food Products Indices are the most relevant for the overall results, as all product groups are included here, this confirms a causal impact of the IPI index on a 1% α -level.

Additionally, the HICP influencing the IPI for Oils & Fats could be due to the important role of Oils & Fats coming from Austria for the whole EU. Although Austria ranks as the 20th biggest producer of Oils & Fats within EU nations (IBISWorld, 2024) measured in revenue size, Austria could still have an impact on the overall Imported Price index, as the coefficient is with 0.2575 not very high. The second rather unexpected finding for the Oils & Fats product group was that IPI was granger causing the ACP with a negative sign of -0.1536 . Following (Hatzenbuehler, Abbott and Foster, 2016) long-term changes of import prices via exchange rate changes can have adaptations of national agricultural production prices. This essentially means that a rise in import prices lead the costs for these products to rise and the local market for agricultural products is under pressure and demand is therefore decreasing because of, resulting in falling prices.

While the third hypothesis from the methods section, that suggested a granger causality influence of both ACP on HICP and IPI on ACP and HICP, can be confirmed when it comes to the ACP granger causing the HICP price index for all product groups but Oils & Fats, another linkage has been revealed for indices along the value chain:

The HICP granger caused the ACP with a negative coefficient for Food Products and for Bread & Cereals even with a coefficient of -3.1988 on a 1% α -level. This marks the single highest granger causality influence of all VAR-estimations performed. While the same linkage could also be found for Food Products along the value chain the coefficient was -0.5089 on a 5% level. As (Bareith, Fertő and Podruzsik, 2024) point out “if consumer prices Granger-cause producer prices, it could suggest that demand-side factors are driving the price adjustments in the supply chain.” (ibid., p.4). That is because usually the price transmission effects are passed over in upward direction meaning from ACP to HICP as has been suggested in the third hypothesis in Section 3.1. This would indicate that shocks to the supply side caused e.g. through production costs are passed on to consumers. Likewise, for the opposite case, which is applicable here if prices of wheat-based consumer products like bread are rising suddenly and with high magnitude, this could

lead to demand for the agricultural product falling, after a period or lag. What has already been established, is that the ongoing war in Ukraine caused by Russia hit the market for wheat prices at the start of the war in February of 2022, as Ukraine is the fifth biggest producer of wheat in the world (Devadoss and Ridley, 2024). Therefore, prices were rising sharply at that time and reached peak prices for food products somewhere in 2022 as can be seen in Figure 6. Moreover, prices have also been falling again since the end of 2022. Since it is the Bread & Cereal HICP that is granger causing the ACP with a lag of 10 months and a negative coefficient of over -3 points, this could mark the influence of the Russian Ukrainian war in the empirical study. Another different reasonable explanation for this association are seasonal changes. As mentioned before, because in the metadata it is not explicitly stated that the data is seasonally adjusted, seasonal changes could have a huge impact on the respective food price indices (Eurostat metadata, 2025). For instance, for Bread & Cereals if the harvest of one year is significantly reduced due to weather related issues, it can have a huge impact on the ACP in the supply chain due to consumer prices changing and therefore demand decreasing after 10 months or lags. The impact on the food products ACP, which was significantly lower than for the Bread & Cereal product group could simply be explained by the influence of the Bread Cereals product group on the overall food products. That is, the high Bread & Cereal influence with -3.1988 could potentially influence the whole food product group. Hence, for all granger causality influences, possible economic explanation and interpretation has been found. However, the main insight from the study remains the diesel price index granger causing most product groups ACP and all HICPs.

5.2 Model Quality and Robustness tests

At first, the goodness or fit of the model shall be discussed in this section to check for reliability of the results and methods. Secondly, the results are further assessed concerning economic reasoning and plausibility, plus a comparison of the results with similar papers from the literature review is made to finally draw a conclusion on the results.

Generally, the value of R-Squared was relatively low throughout the VAR-Analysis. This low value for R-Squared and R-Squared Adjusted is due to choosing the first integration of the variables. This can also be seen in the results section of other papers where the same low values for R-Squared can be identified for the first integration I(1) of their respective variables. For instance (Roman, Górecka and Domagała, 2020) concluded that the quality of their model was not satisfactory, the R-Squared values were only 30% for

crude oil and 2% for food prices, due to using I(1) variables for stationarity purposes of the data. If you take the variables in level form and perform a linear regression the R-Squared is about 45 - 50% for all Consumer Price Indices of food prices (see table 6). Based on the R-Squared, and the Log-likelihood alone, the model quality of course cannot be determined.

In order to check for the robustness of the specific VAR-regressions, several different models can be applied. For instance, it can be checked if the errors are normally distributed via the Jarque-Bera test (Derindag *et al.*, 2023), or if the residuals are autocorrelated via a *Lagrange-Multiplier test* (Astaiza-Gómez, 2020). The optimal case for the residuals is called *white noise* which would characterize the residuals as not being autocorrelated and being normally and identically distributed (Moffat and Akpan, 2019).

In the following, the robustness test that was the most important for the study conducted and which was used shall be elaborated. That is the Lagrange-Multiplier test. The reason why this test is so important is that in an autoregressive model, past values play an important role in predicting and explaining the regression and data in the model. (Levendis, 2023) Therefore, autocorrelation in the errors can lead to significantly influencing the model.

The actual examining for model adequacy involves checking for residuals and overfitting (Moffat and Akpan, 2019). Residuals are essentially the difference between estimation results of the model and the actual data (*ibid.*). That is why autocorrelation in the residuals would lead to potentially different outcomes of the model results compared to the actual data.

Moreover, in time-series modelling the goal is to find a good model that fits the data in a way where the true values of the data are best explained by the model (*ibid.*). Furthermore, it is important to achieve *parsimony* in time series models, that is “the principle of model selection with the possibility of having the smallest number of parameters that completely express the linear dependence structure, providing better prediction, and generalization of new observations.” (Moffat and Akpan, 2019, p. 990)⁶ Hence why it was so important during the study to watch for the number of parameters estimated.

⁶ Although the model used at (Moffat and Akpan, 2019) used an ARIMA model, which is basically the univariate version of a multivariate VAR model, the principles discussed here work likewise for a multivariate model.

Coming back to the residuals, independency is the most important feature that residuals should fulfill (ibid.). Furthermore, this implies that residuals are uncorrelated. Here, the beforementioned Lagrange-Multiplier test can be applied (Astaiza-Gómez, 2020), as has been done in the VAR models for the empirical study. Mathematically, the LM-tests' foundation is based on the "stochastic Lagrange multipliers, obtained from the solution of maximizing the likelihood function in a constrained optimization problem." (Astaiza-Gómez, 2020 p. 13) The test has the advantage that for its calculation only the residuals of the least squares regression are required (ibid.).

The LM-test can amongst other purposes be applied to testing for autocorrelation of the residuals. Here, the H_0 is defined as the residuals being independent and the H_1 stating that the residuals follow an autoregressive process. Following the alternative hypothesis of autocorrelation of the errors (ibid.):

$$\mu_t = \epsilon_t + \rho_1\epsilon_{t-1} + \rho_2\epsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \rho_p\epsilon_{t-p} \quad (7)$$

with $\mu_t \sim \text{n.i.i.d}(0; \sigma^2)$ which means that that the whole error term is ranging from 0 to the variance and the individual errors contributing are connected via a ρ_t term (ibid.).

Logically it follows that for the desired null hypothesis $\epsilon_t \sim \text{n.i.i.d}(0; \sigma^2)$ the ρ_t are all zero having no correlation or autocorrelation.

Table 12 in the Appendix Section displays all LM-test results for the VAR-estimations performed.

All VAR models thus do not reject the null hypothesis that residuals are independently distributed on a 1 or 5 percent level. In Table 12 in the Appendix, all other LM-tests for the VAR-Models are stated. The Jarque-Bera test for normalization was rejected for skewness, kurtosis and normalization for all almost all indices throughout the VAR-tests. In addition, all eigenvalues satisfied the stability condition, which fulfilled the stability condition of the VAR-models. Therefore, the data fulfills the required adequacy tests but are not completely white noise.

5.3 Limitations

In the following possible limitations of the conducted empirical study are discussed. After identifying that there is a positive influence of energy prices in the form of diesel prices on food prices for two steps along the value chain except for Oils & Fats and Bread &

Cereals ACP plus PPIId of combined food products as the main result of the empirical study, some limitations of the study must be addressed:

Firstly, the study by (Derindag *et al.*, 2023) presented in 2.3 researched the linkage of nine independent factors on food prices such as temperature, interest rates and crude-oil. As not only crude oil showed a significant linkage with food products, obviously energy prices are not the only parameter responsible for having a causal impact on food prices. This is also intuitively reasonable, since for instance for the cultivation of several seeds for instance for Oils & Fats and Cereal products, fertilizer is needed in order for wheat or other products to grow. Besides, (Adjemian *et al.*, 2024) explained that recent food prices starting in the middle of 2021 were surging with the fastest pace in the US since decades ago. The supply chain issues themselves during the Covid-19 pandemic, plus labor shortages and rising transportation costs and wages were mostly responsible for the rise on the supply side. That is most of the observed changes in food prices were taking place due to supply side influences. Consequently, the food industry is also an industry that is embedded in and hence largely affected by the state of the local and world economy because of dependencies of the supply chains not only coming from the supply, but also from the demand side.

Secondly, the results rely on the Austrian Institutes that report the data of the PPIId and the other food price indices to the EU (Eurostat metadata, 2025). Inaccuracies and errors in data preparation cannot be accounted for here by the author since he has adopted the data as it has been published on the official EU's website.

The same applies to the diesel price index from the EU's weekly oil bulletin. Contrary to the food price indices, however, here additional responsibility for preparing the data is arising on the authors side since the weekly prices were calculated into monthly prices via the technique described in Section 3.2.

Thirdly, the fact that different lags have been used, especially for the bivariate VAR-Models makes the data less comparable. Nonetheless, (Obadi, S., Korcek, M., 2014) used different lags for their respective bivariate VAR-models as well.

Fourthly, as has been seen in Section 2, the total number of observations and time-span covered leaves room for improvement, since some papers used approximately double the number of observations. However, the period from January 2005 until March 2024 covers two important spikes in the food price market, that also affected the Austrian market. What's more is that the food price monitoring tool only started its data collection of the

respective food price indices in 2005 and thus a time-series study along the value chain for Austrian food prices or price indices could have only been conducted since that time. While different Consumer Prices and Expenditures exist for Austria, for instance from (Statistik Austria, 2024), no indices along the value chain apart from the ones used in this elaboration exist, at least to the authors knowledge.

6 CONCLUSION

The underlying empirical study has been concerned with identifying a possible causal linkage of energy prices in form of diesel prices on several food product groups along the value chain in Austria. Thus, three specific research questions have been posed. To answer the research questions accordingly, a time-series model, that is a VAR-model, has been set up with *granger causality* as the method for checking the causal influence. In order to find the optimal lag length, the AIC, SBIC and HQIC have been taken as selection criteria, as well as the Lagrange-Multiplier model for checking the autocorrelation of residuals.

All in all, the research questions posed in the third section were answered during the phase of the research. Nonetheless, they shall now be summarized again to draw a final conclusion to the study.

The first and most central research question to the study, that is checking for the influence of diesel prices on the respective food price indices has been found to have a significant influence for all food products along the value chain except for Bread & Cereals and Oils & Fats ACP, plus the food products PPI. Additionally, there have been found to be bivariate relationships, that show an influence of food indices on the diesel price index especially for the Oils & Fats and Bread & Cereal product groups. In that case, a significant linkage due to biodiesel production and prices in Austria could be identified, that is either influencing the biodiesel price with a positive coefficient because they are contributing to the whole production of regular diesel. On the other side biodiesel represents a competitive product, since pure biodiesel is sold as well in Austria. Additionally, bio-petrol is produced in Austria as well, which can serve as a competitive product as well (FCIO - Fachverband der Chemischen Industrie Österreichs, 2025).

Moreover, the second research hypothesis, stating that the gross diesel price index created by the author using the weekly oil bulletin by the EU for Austria has a bigger impact on the ACP than on the HICP has been rejected. The higher impact on the final consumer prices of food can be explained by more steps being in between the final retail products that need more energy intensive steps along the production and manufacturing process.

As has been hypothesized in the third hypothesis, the ACP has been found to be the most significant index within the value chain granger causing the HICP except for Oils & Fats products. Additionally, there has also been found a linkage between the HICP and ACP with a negative coefficient to the surprise of the author, since intuitively this linkage has

not been expected. One possible explanation for this linkage is the ongoing war in Ukraine. From the beginning of February 2022 until the end of 2022 prices of wheat-based products were rising rapidly, since there has been a shortage of wheat in the supply chain. As a consequence of high HICP prices of wheat-based bread and flour the ACP prices were lowering with a delay or lag, as demand decreased due to very high prices. This shows the potential influence that the war in Ukraine that has been an inspiration on the topic could have had study along the value chain.

Furthermore, as has been suggested by the WIFO report that the Thesis has been inspired by, a policy suggestion can be derived: The pricing system already established by the ROBVEK-project could be adapted and expanded further for wholesale prices as well (Renhart *et al.*, 2024). As the pricing portal already publishes prices for specific products along the value chain, it is important to keep the current portal as it is and widen the product groups but also single products that are included on the website.

As has been shown in the Theoretical Background part, energy prices and food prices are essential for a societies well-being as well as for environmental sanity. Furthermore, the influence of diesel prices on the food price indices are an indication that due to this dependency it is important to grant subsidies for the farmers that produce the foods that Austrian people eat, especially in times where the diesel price index is rising higher than usually, as it has been during last three years. This issue has been tackled by the Austrian Parliament (Parliament Austria, 2024) by substituting farmers, also in the year 2025, with 7 cents per liter in addition to the already existing refunding of CO₂-pricing, which amounted to 13.5 cents per liter bought for farming equipment. Regardless of these recent measures from the Austrian government, Austrian farmers still have to pay the third highest amount of taxes for agricultural diesel relatively to other EU-states (BauernZeitung, 2024). That is why it is particularly important for Austrian farmers and therefore Austrian institutions such as the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Climate and Environmental Protection, Regions and Water Management and likewise the federal states' chambers of agriculture to get involved in assistance for local farmers producing agricultural products for Austria with diesel fueled machinery.

REFERENCE LIST

- Adjemian, M.K. *et al.* (2024) 'Factors affecting recent food price inflation in the United States', *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 46(2), pp. 648–676. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/aapp.13378>.
- Akaike, H. (1974) 'A new look at the statistical model identification', *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 19(6), pp. 716–723. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1974.1100705>.
- Alom, F., Ward, B.D., & Hu, B. (2011) 'Spillover effects of world oil prices on food prices: evidence for Asia and Pacific countries.' Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Spillover-effects-of-world-oil-prices-on-food-for-Alom-Ward/c60f5e6871832072c75ef00a433ccfbccfee3dba> (Accessed: 4 March 2025).
- Anuradha Mittal (2009) 'The 2008 Food Price Crisis: Rethinking Food Security Policies'. UNITED NATIONS CONFERENCE ON TRADE AND DEVELOPMENT. Available at: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/gdsmdpg2420093_en.pdf (Accessed: 8 February 2025).
- Astaiza-Gómez, J.G. (2020) 'Lagrange Multiplier Tests in Applied Research', *Journal de Ciencia e Ingeniería*, 12(1), pp. 13–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46571/JCI.2020.1.2>.
- BAB (2024) 'Prices of agricultural and forestry goods and operating resources'. Available at: <https://preise.agrarforschung.at> (Accessed: 29 November 2024).
- Bareith, T., Fertő, I. and Podruzsik, S. (2024) 'Wheat price dynamics in Hungary: Resilience to shocks', *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 18, p. 101511. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2024.101511>.
- BauernZeitung (2024) 'BauernZeitung – „Unsere Bauern zahlen zu viel für Diesel“'. Available at: https://bauernzeitung.at/unsere-bauern-zahlen-zu-viel-fuer-diesel/?utm_source=chatgpt.com (Accessed: 1 April 2025).
- Beerge, R. and Devarmani, S. (2024) 'Diesel-Powered Engine and Agriculture', in H. Koten (ed.) *Diesel Engines - Current Challenges and Future Perspectives*. IntechOpen. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1003701>.
- Bundeskanzleramt Österreich (1994) *BGBL.Nr. 630/1994*. Available at: https://rdb.manz.at/document/ris.c.BGBL_OS_19940819_0_0630++ (Accessed: 6 March 2025).
- BWB/BU Lebensmittel. Wien (2022) 'Branchenuntersuchung Lebensmittel'. Bundeswettbewerbsbehörde (BWB). Available at: https://www.bwb.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/BU-LM_final_Stand_20231102_final.pdf (Accessed: 2 January 2025).
- Clement, L. (no date) 'AIC vs BIC', *statOmics*, Ghent University. Available at: [https://statomics.github.io/HDDA21/AICvs-BIC.html#:~:text=1%20When%20large%20datasets%20are,\(n\)%20for%20BIC](https://statomics.github.io/HDDA21/AICvs-BIC.html#:~:text=1%20When%20large%20datasets%20are,(n)%20for%20BIC). (Accessed: 5 April 2025).
- Derindag, O.F. *et al.* (2023) 'Food prices response to global and national factors: Evidence beyond asymmetry', *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1), p. 2187128. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2187128>.
- DESTATIS - Statistisches Bundesamt (2022) 'Zu den Auswirkungen der Corona-Krise

auf die Preiserhebung für den Verbrauchpreisindex / Harmonisierten Verbraucherpreisindex'. Available at: https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Wirtschaft/Preise/Verbraucherpreisindex/Methoden/Downloads/corona-vpi-hvpi.pdf?__blob=publication-File&utm_source=chatgpt.com (Accessed: 4 April 2025).

Devadoss, S. and Ridley, W. (2024) 'Impacts of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on the global wheat market', *World Development*, 173, p. 106396. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2023.106396>.

Durlauf, S.N. and Blume, L.E. (eds) (2010) *Macroeconometrics and Time Series Analysis*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230280830>.

econometrics.com (2025) 'Using trend variables'. Available at: <https://www.econometrics.com/intro/trend.htm> (Accessed: 16 January 2024).

Eric (2021) 'Introduction to Granger Causality', *Introduction to Granger Causality*, 29 June. Available at: <https://www.aptech.com/blog/introduction-to-granger-causality/> (Accessed: 3 December 2024).

European Commission (2023) *Economic and distributional effects of higher energy prices on households in the EU*: LU: Publications Office. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2767/49249> (Accessed: 13 December 2024).

European Commission (2024) 'Weekly Oil Bulletin'. Available at: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis/weekly-oil-bulletin_en (Accessed: 8 November 2024).

European Commission. Joint Research Centre. Institute for Prospective Technological Studies (2010) *Environmental impacts of diet changes in the EU*. LU: Publications Office. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2791/88996> (Accessed: 1 March 2025).

Eurostat (2025) 'Food price monitoring tool'. Available at: https://doi.org/10.2908/PRC_FSC_IDX.

Eurostat metadata (2025) 'Reference metadata for Food price monitoring tool of EU'. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/prc_fsc_idx_esms.htm#stat_presDisseminated.

FCIO - Fachverband der Chemischen Industrie Österreichs (2025) 'BIODIESEL'. Available at: <https://www.biokraft-austria.at> (Accessed: 8 March 2025).

Federal Reserve Bank of Dallas (2024) 'Indexing data to a common starting point'. Available at: <https://www.dallasfed.org/research/basics/indexing#:~:text=Indexing%20improves%20the%20ability%20to,is%20possible%20with%20indexed%20data.> (Accessed: 21 December 2024).

Gilbert, C.L. (2010) 'How to Understand High Food Prices', *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 61(2), pp. 398–425. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-9552.2010.00248.x>.

Granger, C.W.J. (1969) 'Investigating Causal Relations by Econometric Models and Cross-spectral Methods', *Econometrica*, 37(3), p. 424. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1912791>.

Guo, Z. (2023) 'Research on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test for Predicting Stock Prices and Returns', *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences*, 44(1), pp. 101–106. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.54254/2754-1169/44/20232198>.

- Harrell, F.E. (2015) *Regression Modeling Strategies: With Applications to Linear Models, Logistic and Ordinal Regression, and Survival Analysis*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Springer Series in Statistics). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19425-7>.
- Hatzenbuehler, P.L., Abbott, P.C. and Foster, K.A. (2016) 'Agricultural Commodity Prices and Exchange Rates under Structural Change'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.22004/AG.ECON.235153>.
- Hey, J.D. (2005) 'Why We Should Not Be Silent About Noise', *Experimental Economics*, 8(4), pp. 325–345. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10683-005-5373-8>.
- Hussain, N. E., Shaari, M. S., & Abdullah, D. N. C. (2018) 'Effects of Retailing Selling Prices of Petrol and Diesel on Food Prices.', *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, pp. 28–32.
- IBISWorld (2024) 'Oil & Fat Production in Austria - Market Size, Industry Analysis, Trends and Forecasts (2024-2029)'. Available at: <https://www.ibisworld.com/austria/industry/oil-fat-production/200136/#RelatedIndustries> (Accessed: 5 April 2025).
- Iowa Farm Bureau (2022) 'The Relationship of Diesel Fuel Prices to Crude Oil Prices Has Changed', 8 September. Available at: <https://www.iowafarmbureau.com/Article/The-Relationship-of-Diesel-Fuel-Prices-to-Crude-Oil-Prices-Has-Changed> (Accessed: 28 February 2025).
- Janda, K. and Křištofuk, L. (2019) 'The Relationship Between Fuel and Food Prices: Methods and Outcomes', *Annual Review of Resource Economics*, 11(1), pp. 195–216. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-resource-100518-094012>.
- Johansen, S. (1995) *Likelihood-Based Inference in Cointegrated Vector Autoregressive Models*. 1st edn. Oxford University Press Oxford. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/0198774508.001.0001>.
- Kirikaleli, D. and Darbaz, I. (2021) 'The Causal Linkage between Energy Price and Food Price', *Energies*, 14(14), p. 4182. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14144182>.
- Kristoufek, L., Janda, K. and Zilberman, D. (2014) 'Price transmission between biofuels, fuels, and food commodities', *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, 8(3), pp. 362–373. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.1464>.
- Leucci, A.C. *et al.* (2014) 'VAR Models for Dynamic Analysis of Prices in the Agri-food System', in C. Zopounidis *et al.* (eds) *Agricultural Cooperative Management and Policy*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 3–21. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-06635-6_1.
- Levendis, J.D. (2023) *Time Series Econometrics: Learning Through Replication*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Springer Texts in Business and Economics). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-37310-7>.
- Liang, Z. and Li, Q. (2012) 'Functional coefficient regression models with time trend', *Journal of Econometrics*, 170(1), pp. 15–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2011.08.009>.
- Lütkepohl, H. (2005) *New introduction to multiple time series analysis*. Berlin: New York : Springer.

- Ma, Z., Xu, R. and Dong, X. (2015) 'World oil prices and agricultural commodity prices: The evidence from China', *Agricultural Economics (Zemědělská ekonomika)*, 61(12), pp. 564–576. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17221/6/2015-AGRICECON>.
- Mahapatra, S. *et al.* (2021) 'Biofuels and their sources of production: A review on cleaner sustainable alternative against conventional fuel, in the framework of the food and energy nexus', *Energy Nexus*, 4, p. 100036. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nexus.2021.100036>.
- Mitchell, D. (2008) 'A Note on Rising Food Prices'. POLICY RESEARCH WORKING PAPER 4682 The World Bank Development Prospects Group. Available at: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/fr/229961468140943023/pdf/WP4682.pdf> (Accessed: 8 February 2025).
- Moffat, I.U. and Akpan, E.A. (2019) 'White Noise Analysis: A Measure of Time Series Model Adequacy', *Applied Mathematics*, 10(11), pp. 989–1003. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4236/am.2019.1011069>.
- Obadi, S., Korcek, M. (2014) 'Are Food Prices Affected by Crude Oil Price: Causality Investigation.', *Review of Integrative Business & Economics Research*, pp. 411–427.
- Parliament Austria (2024) 'PARLAMENTSKORRESPONDENZ NR. 592– Budgetausschuss: Verlängerung der temporären Agrardiesel-Vergütung von 7 Cent pro Liter', 6 June. Available at: https://www.parlament.gv.at/aktuelles/pk/jahr_2024/pk0592 (Accessed: 6 March 2025).
- Pasrun A., Rosnawintang R., La Ode S., La Tondi, La Ode Arsad S. (2018) 'The Causal Relationship between Crude Oil Price, Exchange Rate and Rice Price', *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy, Econjournals*, pp. 90–94.
- Renhart, A. *et al.* (2024) 'Preistransparenz entlang der Lebensmittelwertschöpfungskette. Entwicklung eines Konzepts einer Preisdatenbank zur Erhebung von Daten in der Lebensmittelwertschöpfungskette in Österreich', *Österreichisches Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung* [Preprint].
- Roman, M., Górecka, A. and Domagała, J. (2020) 'The Linkages between Crude Oil and Food Prices', *Energies*, 13(24), p. 6545. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13246545>.
- Schäfer, G. and European Commission (eds) (2008) *European price statistics: an overview*. 2008 edition. Luxembourg: Publications Office.
- Sinabell, F. (2023) 'Robuste Versorgungsketten in der Agrar- und Nahrungsmittelwirtschaft'. Available at: https://dafne.at/content/report_release/b5b6a174-28a1-461e-83a7-76275655f209_0.pdf (Accessed: 4 January 2025).
- StataCorp (2021) 'Stata: Release 17. Statistical Software.' College Station, TX: StataCorp LLC. Available at: <https://www.stata.com/manuals17/ts.pdf> (Accessed: 5 April 2025).
- Statistik Austria (2024) 'Verbraucherpreisindex (VPI/HVPI)'. Available at: <https://www.statistik.at/statistiken/volkswirtschaft-und-oeffentliche-finanzen/preise-und-preisindizes/verbraucherpreisindex-vpi/hvpi> (Accessed: 10 November 2024).
- Tate, A (2023) 'Understanding the Importance of Stationarity in Time Series', 1 December. Available at: <https://hex.tech/blog/stationarity-in-time-series/> (Accessed: 9 January 2025).

The Pennsylvania State University (2025) ‘Multicollinearity’. Available at: <https://online.stat.psu.edu/stat462/node/177/#:~:text=Multicollinearity%20exists%20when%20two%20or,research%20conclusions%20we%20can%20draw>. (Accessed: 1 April 2025).

U.S. Energy Information Administration (2024) ‘Diesel fuel explained Factors affecting diesel prices’. Available at: <https://www.eia.gov/energyexplained/diesel-fuel/factors-affecting-diesel-prices.php> (Accessed: 7 March 2025).

Zhang, Q. *et al.* (2024) ‘The impact of Russia–Ukraine war on crude oil prices: an EMC framework’, *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), p. 8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02526-9>.

Zingbagba, M., Nunes, R. and Fadairo, M. (2020) ‘The impact of diesel price on upstream and downstream food prices: Evidence from São Paulo’, *Energy Economics*, 85, p. 104531. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2019.104531>.

APPENDIX

Table 10: STATA estimation results of ADF (Augmented Dickey Fuller) unit root test for stationarity for all prices with and without first difference, including optimal lag length in parenthesis:

Variable in first differences	Test-Statistics	Crit. Value (1%)	Crit. Value (5%)	Crit. Value (10%)	p-Value	Stationary
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index	-12.059	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_Food_Products_ACP	-5.147	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_BreadCereal_ACP	-5.754	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_Meat_ACP	-5.555	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_OilsFats_ACP	-5.326	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_Food_Products_HICP	-14.034	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_BreadCereal_HICP	-12.926	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_Meat_HICP	-17.784	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_OilsFats_HICP	-11.735	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_Food_Products_ppi	-8.180	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_Food_Products_IPI	-13.435	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_BreadCereal_IPI	-16.097	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_Meat_IPI	-16.717	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
diff_OilsFats_IPI	-21.039	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.0	Yes
Diesel_Gross_Index	-1.862	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.6739	Yes
Food_Products_ACP	-1.560	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.8076	Yes
BreadCereal_ACP	-2.179	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.5015	Yes
Meat_ACP	-1.228	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.9046	Yes
OilsFats_ACP	-2.461	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.3476	Yes
Food_Products_HICP	0.830	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	1.00	Yes
BreadCereal_HICP	1.715	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	1.00	Yes
Meat_HICP	-0.226	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.9911	Yes

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OilsFats_HICP	-0.832	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.9629	Yes
Food_Products_ppi	0.690	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.9970	Yes
Food_Products_IPI	-0.122	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.9928	Yes
BreadCereal_IPI	-1.755	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.7261	Yes
Meat_IPI	-2.274	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.4486	Yes
OilsFats_IPI	-1.828	-3.997	-3.433	-3.133	0.6913	Yes

Source: Created by author in STATA. Note: Test-Statistic given in level and first difference I(1) form with optimal number of lags in parenthesis; ***, ** and * significant at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively. The H_0 for the ADF-test tested here is that the time-series for the respective variables is not stationary. That is, it has a unit root. The alternative hypothesis is that the variables under consideration are stationary.

Table(s) 11: Results from all VAR-estimations performed in STATA

Food Products PPI – Diesel Gross Price Index

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

diff_Food_Products_ppi						
diff_Food_Products_ppi						
L1.	.4941166	.0602262	8.20	0.000	.3760755	.6121578
L9.	.1201713	.063274	1.90	0.058	-.0038435	.2441862
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L1.	.0111557	.007965	1.40	0.161	-.0044556	.0267669
L9.	.0124917	.0082361	1.52	0.129	-.0036507	.0286341
trend	.0004491	.0005557	0.81	0.419	-.0006402	.0015383
_cons	.0294412	.0729446	0.40	0.686	-.1135275	.17241

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
diff_Food_Products_ppi						
L1.	1.400635	.5260522	2.66	0.008	.3695917	2.431678
L9.	-.2849762	.5526741	-0.52	0.606	-1.368198	.7982452
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L1.	.1304662	.0695716	1.88	0.061	-.0058916	.266824
L9.	-.2152189	.0719389	-2.99	0.003	-.3562166	-.0742211
trend	.0005378	.0048542	0.11	0.912	-.0089762	.0100518
_cons	-.0288764	.6371424	-0.05	0.964	-1.277653	1.2199

Meat HICP – Diesel Gross Price Index

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

diff_Meat_HICP						
diff_Meat_HICP						
L1.	-.179944	.0639737	-2.81	0.005	-.3053302	-.0545579
L6.	.176897	.0642694	2.75	0.006	.0509314	.3028626
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L1.	.0456162	.0136675	3.34	0.001	.0188284	.072404
L6.	.0120288	.0138765	0.87	0.386	-.0151688	.0392263
trend	.0020753	.0009987	2.08	0.038	.0001179	.0040327
_cons	.012718	.1324193	0.10	0.923	-.2468191	.2722551

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
diff_Meat_HICP						
L1.	.1041916	.3067377	0.34	0.734	-.4970032	.7053865
L6.	-.4481682	.3081553	-1.45	0.146	-1.052141	.1558051
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L1.	.2114988	.0655321	3.23	0.001	.0830581	.3399394
L6.	.0024453	.0665345	0.04	0.971	-.12796	.1328506
trend	.0025427	.0047884	0.53	0.595	-.0068425	.0119278
_cons	.0049068	.6349171	0.01	0.994	-1.239508	1.249321

Oils & Fats HICP – Diesel Gross Price Index

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

diff_OilsFats_HICP						
diff_OilsFats_HICP						
L1.	.1443192	.0643544	2.24	0.025	.0181869	.2704515
L3.	.124006	.0626074	1.98	0.048	.0012977	.2467143
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L1.	.0551854	.0206209	2.68	0.007	.0147691	.0956017
L3.	.0913877	.0212712	4.30	0.000	.0496969	.1330784
trend	.0016931	.0014581	1.16	0.246	-.0011648	.004551
_cons	.0148061	.1957682	0.08	0.940	-.3688925	.3985048

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
diff_OilsFats_HICP						
L1.	.7683294	.1946908	3.95	0.000	.3867424	1.149916
L3.	-.0279859	.1894056	-0.15	0.883	-.3992141	.3432423
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L1.	.2161192	.0623843	3.46	0.001	.0938481	.3383902
L3.	.0756791	.0643515	1.18	0.240	-.0504475	.2018057
trend	-.0001124	.0044113	-0.03	0.980	-.0087583	.0085336
_cons	-.0360471	.5922557	-0.06	0.951	-1.196847	1.124753

Bread & Cereal HICP – Diesel Gross Price Index

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

diff_BreadCereal_HICP						
diff_BreadCereal_HICP						
L6.	.0929746	.0705958	1.32	0.188	-.0453906	.2313398
L10.	.1874415	.0710246	2.64	0.008	.0482357	.3266472
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L6.	.001244	.0083968	0.15	0.882	-.0152133	.0177014
L10.	.0289047	.0086072	3.36	0.001	.0120349	.0457745
trend	.0012525	.0006222	2.01	0.044	.0000331	.0024719
_cons	.0544148	.0823233	0.66	0.509	-.106936	.2157655

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
diff_BreadCereal_HICP						
L6.	-.2657995	.5681117	-0.47	0.640	-1.379278	.8476789
L10.	-1.831467	.5715627	-3.20	0.001	-2.951709	-.7112247
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L6.	-.0178743	.0675721	-0.26	0.791	-.1503132	.1145645
L10.	.0019238	.0692655	0.03	0.978	-.133834	.1376816
trend	.0066134	.0050069	1.32	0.187	-.0031999	.0164266
_cons	.0753488	.6624878	0.11	0.909	-1.223103	1.373801

Food Products HICP – Diesel Gross Price Index

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

diff_Food_Products_HICP						
diff_Food_Products_HICP						
L8.	.1377919	.0644861	2.14	0.033	.0114016	.2641823
L9.	-.0174067	.064452	-0.27	0.787	-.1437302	.1089169
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L8.	.0243799	.0098083	2.49	0.013	.0051559	.0436039
L9.	.0307793	.0098258	3.13	0.002	.011521	.0500375
trend	.0014362	.0007089	2.03	0.043	.0000467	.0028256
_cons	.0492159	.0934124	0.53	0.598	-.133869	.2323009

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
diff_Food_Products_HICP						
L8.	-.1197568	.4475462	-0.27	0.789	-.9969313	.7574177
L9.	-1.276662	.4473097	-2.85	0.004	-2.153373	-.3999509
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L8.	-.0094035	.0680718	-0.14	0.890	-.1428217	.1240147
L9.	-.1969683	.0681931	-2.89	0.004	-.3306244	-.0633122
trend	.0054892	.00492	1.12	0.265	-.0041539	.0151322
_cons	.0163301	.6483008	0.03	0.980	-1.254316	1.286976

Food Products ACP – Diesel Gross Price Index

		Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
diff_Food_Products_ACP							
	diff_Food_Products_ACP						
	L5.	-.2765403	.0675644	-4.09	0.000	-.408964	-.1441165
	L10.	-.0254405	.0677801	-0.38	0.707	-.1582871	.1074062
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
	L5.	.0711485	.031971	2.23	0.026	.0084866	.1338104
	L10.	.0260159	.0330114	0.79	0.431	-.0386852	.090717
	trend	.0014829	.002328	0.64	0.524	-.0030799	.0060457
	_cons	.1472569	.3154083	0.47	0.641	-.4709321	.7654459
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
	diff_Food_Products_ACP						
	L5.	.0752446	.144967	0.52	0.604	-.2088854	.3593747
	L10.	.0699788	.1454299	0.48	0.630	-.2150587	.3550162
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
	L5.	-.1408618	.0685973	-2.05	0.040	-.27531	-.0064136
	L10.	-.0462753	.0708297	-0.65	0.514	-.1850989	.0925483
	trend	.0021405	.004995	0.43	0.668	-.0076495	.0119304
	_cons	.0409696	.6767441	0.06	0.952	-1.285425	1.367364

Bread & Cereal ACP – Diesel Gross Price Index

		Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
diff_BreadCereal_ACP							
	diff_BreadCereal_ACP						
	L5.	-.2241825	.0669084	-3.35	0.001	-.3553205	-.0930445
	L10.	-.0419786	.0697027	-0.60	0.547	-.1785932	.0946361
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
	L5.	.0192698	.1644742	0.12	0.907	-.3030937	.3416332
	L10.	.0711736	.164674	0.43	0.666	-.2515815	.3939286
	trend	-.0070961	.0116632	-0.61	0.543	-.0299555	.0157633
	_cons	1.254077	1.598397	0.78	0.433	-1.878723	4.386877
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
	diff_BreadCereal_ACP						
	L5.	.0826953	.0277622	2.98	0.003	.0282823	.1371083
	L10.	.0163071	.0289217	0.56	0.573	-.0403783	.0729925
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
	L5.	-.1512504	.0682451	-2.22	0.027	-.2850084	-.0174924
	L10.	-.0359922	.068328	-0.53	0.598	-.1699127	.0979283
	trend	.002811	.0048394	0.58	0.561	-.006674	.012296
	_cons	-.0123055	.6632214	-0.02	0.985	-1.312196	1.287585

Oils & Fats ACP – Diesel Gross Price Index

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

diff_OilsFats_ACP						
diff_OilsFats_ACP						
L9.	-.2893755	.099696	-2.90	0.004	-.484776	-.093975
L10.	.5720942	.0994887	5.75	0.000	.3770999	.7670885

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L9.	-.001817	.0623025	-0.03	0.977	-.1239276	.1202936
L10.	-.0930124	.0624284	-1.49	0.136	-.2153699	.029345
trend	-.0032475	.0043752	-0.74	0.458	-.0118227	.0053276
_cons	.553715	.6004372	0.92	0.356	-.6231203	1.73055

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
diff_OilsFats_ACP						
L9.	-.2308392	.1094278	-2.11	0.035	-.4453137	-.0163647
L10.	.2517129	.1092003	2.31	0.021	.0376843	.4657415

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L9.	-.2200206	.0683841	-3.22	0.001	-.3540511	-.0859902
L10.	.0301076	.0685224	0.44	0.660	-.1041937	.164409
trend	.002149	.0048022	0.45	0.655	-.0072632	.0115612
_cons	.0778021	.6590486	0.12	0.906	-1.213909	1.369514

Meat ACP – Diesel Gross Price Index

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	

diff_Meat_ACP						
diff_Meat_ACP						
L9.	-.3579261	.1011411	-3.54	0.000	-.556159	-.1596932
L10.	.2081263	.0992488	2.10	0.036	.0136022	.4026504

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L9.	.0653557	.024164	2.70	0.007	.0179952	.1127161
L10.	.0921399	.0244518	3.77	0.000	.0442153	.1400645
trend	.0020076	.0016904	1.19	0.235	-.0013056	.0053208
_cons	.0173027	.2294719	0.08	0.940	-.432454	.4670595

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
diff_Meat_ACP						
L9.	-.3416078	.2936759	-1.16	0.245	-.917202	.2339865
L10.	.094248	.2881815	0.33	0.744	-.4705774	.6590734

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2						
L9.	-.2039794	.0701631	-2.91	0.004	-.3414966	-.0664622
L10.	.0480363	.0709988	0.68	0.499	-.0911188	.1871915
trend	.0030404	.0049084	0.62	0.536	-.0065799	.0126608
_cons	.0240183	.6663008	0.04	0.971	-1.281907	1.329944

Food Products Along the Value Chain with Diesel Gross Price Index

Vector autoregression

Sample: 2005m12 thru 2024m3	Number of obs	=	220
Log likelihood = -1809.525	AIC	=	16.72296
FPE = 12.59929	HQIC	=	16.90984
Det(Sigma_ml) = 9.591195	SBIC	=	17.18573

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
diff_Food_Pr~ACP	6	2.21252	0.0701	16.593	0.0053
diff_Food_Pr~ICP	6	.671215	0.0922	22.35051	0.0004
diff_Food_Prod~I	6	1.10202	0.0183	4.098616	0.5353
diff_Food_Prod~i	6	.605776	0.0952	23.14166	0.0003
diff_Diesel_Gr~2	6	4.68072	0.0305	6.918823	0.2267

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]
diff_Food_Products_ACP					
diff_Food_Products_ACP					
L10.	.1281932	.0672424	1.91	0.057	-.0035994 .2599858
diff_Food_Products_HICP					
L10.	-.5000077	.231617	-2.16	0.031	-.9539687 -.0460467
diff_Food_Products_IPI					
L10.	-.1000625	.1614433	-0.62	0.535	-.4164856 .2163606
diff_Food_Products_ppi					
L10.	-.5653242	.3027913	-1.87	0.062	-1.158784 .0281358
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2					
L10.	.0308527	.0355027	0.87	0.385	-.0387312 .1004367
_cons	.5197585	.1630039	3.19	0.001	.2002767 .8392402
diff_Food_Products_HICP					
diff_Food_Products_HICP					
L10.	.0429044	.0203994	2.10	0.035	.0029223 .0828866
diff_Food_Products_HICP					
L10.	.0266893	.0702661	0.38	0.704	-.1110297 .1644082
diff_Food_Products_IPI					
L10.	.0901192	.0489774	1.84	0.066	-.0058746 .186113
diff_Food_Products_ppi					
L10.	.0864031	.0918583	0.94	0.347	-.0936359 .2664421
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2					
L10.	.0120791	.0107705	1.12	0.262	-.0090307 .0331889
_cons	.1939435	.0494508	3.92	0.000	.0970217 .2908652
diff_Food_Products_IPI					
diff_Food_Products_IPI					
L10.	.0323049	.0334924	0.96	0.335	-.0333389 .0979488
diff_Food_Products_HICP					
L10.	.0745607	.1153648	0.65	0.518	-.1515502 .3006716
diff_Food_Products_IPI					
L10.	.0118062	.0804124	0.15	0.883	-.1457992 .1694117
diff_Food_Products_ppi					
L10.	.1284557	.1508156	0.85	0.394	-.1671375 .4240489
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2					
L10.	-.0035661	.0176833	-0.20	0.840	-.0382247 .0310926
_cons	.2688944	.0811897	3.31	0.001	.1097655 .4280233
diff_Food_Products_ppi					
diff_Food_Products_ppi					
L10.	.0346673	.0184106	1.88	0.060	-.0014169 .0707515
diff_Food_Products_HICP					
L10.	-.018357	.0634156	-0.29	0.772	-.1426493 .1059354
diff_Food_Products_IPI					
L10.	-.0316444	.0442024	-0.72	0.474	-.1182795 .0549908

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diff_Food_Products_ppi	L10.	.1945893	.0829028	2.35	0.019	.0321027	.3570758	
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	.0202181	.0097205	2.08	0.038	.0011663	.0392698	
	_cons	.1863558	.0446297	4.18	0.000	.0988832	.2738284	
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	diff_Food_Products_ACP	L10.	.1442585	.1422554	1.01	0.311	-.134557	.4230739
diff_Food_Products_HICP	L10.	-.7919861	.4900002	-1.62	0.106	-1.752369	.1683967	
diff_Food_Products_IPI	L10.	-.4672678	.3415435	-1.37	0.171	-1.136681	.2021451	
diff_Food_Products_ppi	L10.	.0915835	.6405738	0.14	0.886	-1.163918	1.347085	
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	-.0073035	.0751081	-0.10	0.923	-.1545127	.1399057	
	_cons	.5788381	.3448449	1.68	0.093	-.0970456	1.254722	

Oils & Fats with Diesel Gross Price Index

Vector autoregression

Sample: 2005m12 thru 2024m3
 Log likelihood = -2270.29
 FPE = 12956.35
 Det(Sigma_ml) = 10802.06
 Number of obs = 220
 AIC = 20.82082
 HQIC = 20.9454
 SBIC = 21.12933

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
diff_OilsFat~ACP	5	4.19868	0.1480	38.21637	0.0000
diff_OilsFat~ICP	5	1.58718	0.0296	6.718423	0.1515
diff_OilsFats~I	5	3.49426	0.0270	6.103194	0.1916
diff_Diesel_Gr~2	5	4.72699	0.0066	1.463008	0.8332

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
diff_OilsFats_ACP						
diff_OilsFats_ACP	L10.	.358525	.0629981	5.69	0.000	.235051 .4819991
diff_OilsFats_HICP	L10.	-.2727681	.1836143	-1.49	0.137	-.6326455 .0871093
diff_OilsFats_IPI	L10.	-.1472625	.0817067	-1.80	0.071	-.3074046 .0128797
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	-.0966934	.0616466	-1.57	0.117	-.2175185 .0241317
	_cons	.2898309	.2875164	1.01	0.313	-.2736908 .8533527
diff_OilsFats_HICP						
diff_OilsFats_ACP	L10.	.0122342	.0238145	0.51	0.607	-.0344414 .0589097
diff_OilsFats_HICP	L10.	-.0960762	.0694097	-1.38	0.166	-.2321167 .0399642
diff_OilsFats_IPI	L10.	-.0469185	.0308867	-1.52	0.129	-.1074553 .0136183
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	.0362826	.0233036	1.56	0.119	-.0093916 .0819567
	_cons	.4023904	.1086866	3.70	0.000	.1893685 .6154123
diff_OilsFats_IPI						
diff_OilsFats_ACP	L10.	-.0801622	.0524289	-1.53	0.126	-.1829209 .0225966
diff_OilsFats_HICP	L10.	.2547284	.1528093	1.67	0.096	-.0447723 .5542292
diff_OilsFats_IPI						

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	L10.	.0470449	.0679988	0.69	0.489	-.0862302	.18032
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	.0491853	.0513041	0.96	0.338	-.0513689	.1497396
	_cons	.3408495	.2392797	1.42	0.154	-.1281302	.8098291

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	diff_OilsFats_ACP						
	L10.	.0695352	.0709251	0.98	0.327	-.0694753	.2085458
	diff_OilsFats_HICP						
	L10.	-.1498391	.2067182	-0.72	0.469	-.5549993	.2553212
	diff_OilsFats_IPI						
	L10.	-.0154682	.0919877	-0.17	0.866	-.1957608	.1648244
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	-.02073	.0694035	-0.30	0.765	-.1567583	.1152983
	_cons	.3389319	.3236942	1.05	0.295	-.295497	.9733608

Bread & Cereal Along the Value Chain with Diesel Prices

Vector autoregression

Sample: 2005m12 thru 2024m3
 Log likelihood = -2146.795
 FPE = 4216.087
 Det(Sigma_ml) = 3515.065
 Number of obs = 220
 AIC = 19.69814
 HQIC = 19.82272
 SBIC = 20.00665

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
diff_BreadCe~ICP	5	.562827	0.1697	44.97589	0.0000
diff_BreadCe~ACP	5	11.2305	0.0283	6.401926	0.1711
diff_BreadCere~I	5	2.26006	0.0115	2.563344	0.6333
diff_Diesel_Gr~2	5	4.61826	0.0518	12.01318	0.0173

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
diff_BreadCereal_HICP						
diff_BreadCereal_HICP	L10.	.1989188	.0650583	3.06	0.002	.0714069 .3264306
diff_BreadCereal_ACP	L10.	.0078561	.0035139	2.24	0.025	.0009691 .0147432
diff_BreadCereal_IPI	L10.	.0454423	.0184075	2.47	0.014	.0093642 .0815204
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	.0279123	.0082682	3.38	0.001	.011707 .0441176
	_cons	.2105679	.0417244	5.05	0.000	.1287895 .2923463

diff_BreadCereal_ACP	diff_BreadCereal_HICP					
	L10.	-3.220231	1.298152	-2.48	0.013	-5.764563 -.6758992
diff_BreadCereal_ACP	L10.	.0306778	.0701146	0.44	0.662	-.1067442 .1680998
diff_BreadCereal_IPI	L10.	.1028852	.367298	0.28	0.779	-.6170057 .8227761
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	.0908957	.1649802	0.55	0.582	-.2324595 .4142509
	_cons	1.203367	.8325565	1.45	0.148	-.4284134 2.835148

diff_BreadCereal_IPI	diff_BreadCereal_HICP					
	L10.	-.3943543	.2612452	-1.51	0.131	-.9063854 .1176767
diff_BreadCereal_ACP	L10.	.0036566	.0141101	0.26	0.796	-.0239987 .031312
diff_BreadCereal_IPI	L10.	-.0208476	.0739165	-0.28	0.778	-.1657212 .124026
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2	L10.	.0010954	.0332012	0.03	0.974	-.0639778 .0661686

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_cons		.1288325	.1759673	0.73	0.464	-.2160572	.4737221

diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
diff_Meat_HICP							
L10.		-.0823917	.3326939	-0.25	0.804	-.7344598	.5696764
diff_Meat_ACP							
L10.		-.2026596	.2113493	-0.96	0.338	-.6168965	.2115773
diff_Meat_IPI							
L10.		-.0206997	.1392799	-0.15	0.882	-.2936833	.2522838
diff_Diesel_Gross_Index_2							
L10.		.0011196	.0713957	0.02	0.987	-.1388135	.1410526
_cons		.3640682	.3278984	1.11	0.267	-.2786009	1.006737

Food Products Along the Value Chain

Vector autoregression

Sample: 2005m12 thru 2024m3
 Log likelihood = -1182.733
 FPE = .6586618
 Det(Sigma_ml) = .549144

Number of obs = 220
 AIC = 10.93393
 HQIC = 11.05852
 SBIC = 11.24244

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
diff_Food_Pr~ACP	5	2.21115	0.0669	15.78361	0.0033
diff_Food_Pr~ICP	5	.671564	0.0870	20.97285	0.0003
diff_Food_Prod~I	5	1.09956	0.0181	4.057198	0.3983
diff_Food_Prod~i	5	.610279	0.0774	18.45262	0.0010

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]		
diff_Food_Products_ACP							
diff_Food_Products_ACP							
L10.		.1310853	.0672751	1.95	0.051	-.0007715	.2629421
diff_Food_Products_HICP							
L10.		-.5088676	.2317893	-2.20	0.028	-.9631663	-.0545689
diff_Food_Products_IPI							
L10.		-.1121217	.1611217	-0.70	0.487	-.4279144	.203671
diff_Food_Products_ppi							
L10.		-.4627886	.279335	-1.66	0.098	-1.010275	.084698
_cons		.508922	.162805	3.13	0.002	.1898301	.8280138

diff_Food_Products_HICP							
diff_Food_Products_ACP							
L10.		.0440367	.0204326	2.16	0.031	.0039896	.0840839
diff_Food_Products_HICP							
L10.		.0232205	.0703983	0.33	0.742	-.1147576	.1611987
diff_Food_Products_IPI							
L10.		.0853979	.0489354	1.75	0.081	-.0105136	.1813095
diff_Food_Products_ppi							
L10.		.1265465	.0848388	1.49	0.136	-.0397344	.2928274
_cons		.1897009	.0494466	3.84	0.000	.0927873	.2866145

diff_Food_Products_IPI							
diff_Food_Products_ACP							
L10.		.0319706	.0334544	0.96	0.339	-.0335988	.0975401
diff_Food_Products_HICP							
L10.		.0755847	.1152637	0.66	0.512	-.1503279	.3014974
diff_Food_Products_IPI							
L10.		.0132	.0801222	0.16	0.869	-.1438366	.1702367
diff_Food_Products_ppi							
L10.		.1166043	.1389071	0.84	0.401	-.1556486	.3888573
_cons		.270147	.0809593	3.34	0.001	.1114697	.4288242

diff_Food_Products_ppi							

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diff_Food_Products_ACP							
L10.		.0365626	.018568	1.97	0.049	.00017	.0729552
diff_Food_Products_HICP							
L10.		-.0241629	.0639741	-0.38	0.706	-.1495498	.1012239
diff_Food_Products_IPI							
L10.		-.0395469	.0444697	-0.89	0.374	-.1267059	.0476122
diff_Food_Products_ppi							
L10.		.2617817	.0770967	3.40	0.001	.1106749	.4128885
_cons		.1792545	.0449343	3.99	0.000	.0911849	.2673241

Bread & Cereal Along the Value Chain

Vector autoregression

Sample: 2005m12 thru 2024m3 Number of obs = 220
 Log likelihood = -1507.26 AIC = 13.81146
 FPE = 199.9045 HQIC = 13.88621
 Det(Sigma_ml) = 179.242 SBIC = 13.99657

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
diff_BreadCe~ICP	4	.575883	0.1267	31.92552	0.0000
diff_BreadCe~ACP	4	11.2122	0.0269	6.089978	0.1073
diff_BreadCere~I	4	2.25483	0.0115	2.562242	0.4641

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
diff_BreadCereal_HICP						
L10.		.2055049	.0666921	3.08	0.002	.0747909 .336219
diff_BreadCereal_ACP						
L10.		.0084524	.0035992	2.35	0.019	.0013982 .0155067
diff_BreadCereal_IPI						
L10.		.0480592	.0188615	2.55	0.011	.0110913 .0850272
_cons		.2150303	.04277	5.03	0.000	.1312026 .298858
diff_BreadCereal_ACP						
L10.		-3.198783	1.298463	-2.46	0.014	-5.743725 -.6538419
diff_BreadCereal_ACP						
L10.		.0326197	.0700742	0.47	0.642	-.1047232 .1699626
diff_BreadCereal_IPI						
L10.		.1114073	.3672253	0.30	0.762	-.608341 .8311556
_cons		1.217899	.8327124	1.46	0.144	-.4141873 2.849985
diff_BreadCereal_IPI						
L10.		-.3940959	.2611283	-1.51	0.131	-.9058979 .1177062
diff_BreadCereal_ACP						
L10.		.00368	.0140923	0.26	0.794	-.0239404 .0313005
diff_BreadCereal_IPI						
L10.		-.0207449	.0738511	-0.28	0.779	-.1654904 .1240005
_cons		.4401788	.1674632	2.63	0.009	.1119571 .7684006

Meat Prices Along the Value Chain

Vector autoregression

Sample: 2005m7 thru 2024m3 Number of obs = 225
 Log likelihood = -1249.225 AIC = 11.21089
 FPE = 14.83914 HQIC = 11.28442
 Det(Sigma_ml) = 13.33764 SBIC = 11.39308

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
diff_Meat_HICP	4	.99984	0.0255	5.882412	0.1175

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diff_Meat_ACP	4	1.68231	0.0097	2.212596	0.5295
diff_Meat_IPI	4	2.55067	0.0034	.7722601	0.8561

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
diff_Meat_HICP						
diff_Meat_HICP						
L5.	-.0017837	.0700937	-0.03	0.980	-.1391649	.1355975
diff_Meat_ACP						
L5.	.1005212	.0435072	2.31	0.021	.0152486	.1857938
diff_Meat_IPI						
L5.	-.0436601	.0292329	-1.49	0.135	-.1009556	.0136354
_cons	.2634182	.068669	3.84	0.000	.1288294	.3980071
diff_Meat_ACP						
diff_Meat_HICP						
L5.	-.0268998	.1179382	-0.23	0.820	-.2580544	.2042549
diff_Meat_ACP						
L5.	-.0654976	.0732044	-0.89	0.371	-.2089755	.0779803
diff_Meat_IPI						
L5.	-.0301396	.0491867	-0.61	0.540	-.1265438	.0662646
_cons	.2695847	.1155411	2.33	0.020	.0431283	.4960411
diff_Meat_IPI						
diff_Meat_HICP						
L5.	-.0905644	.1788147	-0.51	0.613	-.4410349	.259906
diff_Meat_ACP						
L5.	-.0301216	.1109904	-0.27	0.786	-.2476589	.1874157
diff_Meat_IPI						
L5.	.0602077	.0745756	0.81	0.419	-.0859578	.2063731
_cons	.2868321	.1751803	1.64	0.102	-.0565149	.6301791

Oils & Fats Along the Value Chain

Vector autoregression

Sample: 2005m12 thru 2024m3	Number of obs	=	220
Log likelihood = -1622.244	AIC	=	14.85677
FPE = 568.5825	HQIC	=	14.93152
Det(Sigma_ml) = 509.8128	SBIC	=	15.04187

Equation	Parms	RMSE	R-sq	chi2	P>chi2
diff_OilsFat~ACP	4	4.2123	0.1385	35.36071	0.0000
diff_OilsFat~ICP	4	1.5922	0.0189	4.247521	0.2359
diff_OilsFats~I	4	3.49344	0.0229	5.162519	0.1603

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]
diff_OilsFats_ACP					
diff_OilsFats_ACP					
L10.	.3528532	.0632449	5.58	0.000	.2288954 .476811
diff_OilsFats_HICP					
L10.	-.2782321	.1846049	-1.51	0.132	-.640051 .0835868
diff_OilsFats_IPI					
L10.	-.153649	.0820602	-1.87	0.061	-.314484 .007186
_cons	.2682154	.2887872	0.93	0.353	-.2977972 .834228
diff_OilsFats_HICP					
diff_OilsFats_ACP					
L10.	.0143624	.0239058	0.60	0.548	-.0324922 .061217
diff_OilsFats_HICP					
L10.	-.094026	.0697785	-1.35	0.178	-.2307892 .0427373
diff_OilsFats_IPI					
L10.	-.044522	.0310178	-1.44	0.151	-.1053158 .0162717
_cons	.4105012	.1091582	3.76	0.000	.1965551 .6244473
diff_OilsFats_IPI					
diff_OilsFats_ACP					
L10.	-.0772771	.0524517	-1.47	0.141	-.1800805 .0255264
diff_OilsFats_HICP					
L10.	.2575078	.1531006	1.68	0.093	-.0425639 .5575795
diff_OilsFats_IPI					
L10.	.0502936	.068056	0.74	0.460	-.0830937 .1836809
_cons	.3518447	.2395035	1.47	0.142	-.1175734 .8212629

Table 12: Lagrange Multiplier test for autocorrelation of the residuals results for all VAR-estimation Models:

VAR-Estimation	LM-test results
Food Products ACP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.72292 (5); 0.26183 (10)
Oils & Fats ACP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.29721(9); 0.61340 (10)
Bread & Cereal ACP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.59736 (5); 0.00183 (10)
Meat Products ACP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.17411 (9); 0.13871 (10)
Food Products HICP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.41283 (8); 0.42020 (9)
Oils & Fats HICP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.10252 (1); 0.14706 (3)
Bread & Cereal HICP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.30320 (6); 0.30610 (10)
Meat Products HICP <-> Diesel Price Index	0.10162 (1); 0.11710 (6)
Food Products PPI <-> Diesel Price Index	0.22615 (1); 0.28148 (9)
Food Products along the value chain	0.40609 (10)
Bread & Cereal along the value chain	0.12604 (10)
Oils & Fats along the value chain	0.84268 (10)
Meat Products along the value chain	0.46561 (5)
Food Products along the value chain with Diesel	0.69508 (10)
Bread & Cereal along the value chain with Diesel	0.09780 (10)
Oils & Fats along the value chain with Diesel	0.50599 (10)
Meat Products along the value chain with Diesel	0.19697 (10)

Source: created by author using VAR-estimations in STATA.

Note: The coefficients on the right-hand side represent the Prob > chi2 and numbers in parenthesis are optimal lag numbers identified with AIC, SBIC and HQIC. Note also that for the bivariate VAR-Models always two lags were chosen and for products along the value chain only one due to the number of parameters limited to 22 since in total observations 220 were used. Following The H_0 states that there is no autocorrelation of the residuals (Johansen, 1995 p. 21-22) which is desired. Thus the H_1 says that there is autocorrelation of the residuals. Consequently, all p-values exceeding 0.05 or 0.10 (on a 5 and 10 percent level respectively) reject the null hypothesis, except for the bivariate estimation with Bread & Cereal ACP of the 10th lag. For Food Products with diesel 30 parameters were estimated, which is strictly speaking disregarding the *parsimony* principle or rule of thumb by (Harrell , 2015).

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